

Skyline Sampling

Choosing Representative Objects from Skylines by Combining Low-Dimensional Subset Skylines

Stefan Schnürle

Competence Center Distributed Secure Software Systems (D3S)
Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts
6048 Horw, Switzerland
stefan.schnuerle@hslu.ch

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Advisor: Dr. Ruedi Arnold
Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts, 6048 Horw, Switzerland
ruedi.arnold@hslu.ch

Expert: Dr. Stanislas Nanchen
Ergon Informatik AG, 8032 Zürich, Switzerland
stanislas.nanchen@ergon.ch

Abstract

The calculation of the *skyline* over a database with respect to a user's individual *preferences* has attracted much attention in recent years, since it can be applied to a broad range of scenarios: e-commerce, multi-criteria decision-making, or database visualization, to name but a few. The skyline consists of the *most interesting* objects of a database. The concept of *interestingness* is captured by the paradigm of *Pareto dominance*, which guarantees an *absolute fairness* when it comes to deciding which objects should be contained in the skyline. However, as attractive as the property of absolute fairness may seem, it suffers from certain inherent weaknesses which are rooted in the *curse of dimensionality*, and are therefore especially prominent when calculating high-dimensional skylines, i.e., calculations with user-defined preferences over many database attributes. Namely, these weaknesses are excessive runtime and unmanageable skyline size. The more dimensions there are, the more apparent these issues become. Even though research efforts have come up with a wide variety of algorithms for the calculation of skylines, they all respect the Pareto dominance paradigm, and therefore cannot be drawn upon in order to attack its inherent issues. Instead, a family of alternative algorithms - mostly heuristics - has been proposed to mitigate the mentioned shortcomings. The randomized *skyline sampling algorithm* is one of them and is based upon the idea of calculating a number of low-dimensional *subset skylines*, so called *topics of interest*, of only a subset of the user's preferences, and combining them to finally report a *skyline sample*. In this work, this algorithm is investigated, implemented, integrated into the existing *prefSQL framework* and reviewed with respect to its runtime, the manageability of the skyline sample's size and, probably most interesting, to the sample's *representativeness* with respect to the entire skyline. It will be shown that the skyline sampling algorithm generally performs quite satisfactory, but that there are certain conditions when this is not the case and other approaches might prove more beneficial.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Skyline Queries

Skyline queries as proposed by S. Börzsöny *et al.* in [1] have attracted the database community’s attention in recent years as pointed out in [2, 3], since they allow for the retrieval of the *most interesting* objects from a database in a more intuitive way than standard SQL queries. The concept of *interestingness* is captured by the paradigm of *Pareto dominance* as defined in [definition 1.1](#), and manifests in the user’s ability to specify personalized, individual preferences over the database’s attributes. As shown in [example 1.1](#), these preferences can be formulated in a more natural way than it would be possible in standard SQL.

Definition 1.1 (Pareto Dominance):

Given a database object $\mathbf{o} \in D_1 \times D_2 \times \dots \times D_d$ (i.e., a d -tuple (o_1, o_2, \dots, o_d) over the d attributes’ domain) and another database object $\mathbf{p} \in D_1 \times D_2 \times \dots \times D_d : (p_1, p_2, \dots, p_d)$, \mathbf{o} is said to *dominate* \mathbf{p} iff:

$$\forall i \in [1, d] \subset \mathbb{N} : o_i \succeq_i p_i \wedge \exists i \in [1, d] \subset \mathbb{N} : o_i \succ_i p_i.$$

Following the terminology in [2], the notion of “ $o_i \succ_i p_i$ ” is interpreted as “ \mathbf{o} *dominates* \mathbf{p} ”, or, equivalently, \mathbf{o} is *preferred* over \mathbf{p} , with respect to the user’s preference specified over database attribute i ”. Analogously, $o_i \succeq_i p_i$ is interpreted as “ \mathbf{o} either *dominates* or is equivalent to \mathbf{p} with respect to the user’s preference specified over database attribute i ”.

Example 1.1

An example of a *skyline query* as implemented in the *prefSQL framework* in [4] is shown. The user doesn't have to specify "classic" hard constraints via WHERE-clauses, but can query the database by providing a more natural formulation of her preferences:

```
SELECT * FROM cars SKYLINE OF cars.price LOW, cars.mileage LOW, colors.name
('red' >> 'black' >> OTHERS EQUAL);
```

This example returns all *dominating* (refer to [section 1.1](#)) cars of the AutoScout24's database (see [section 1.3](#)) with a low price, a low mileage and the color red preferred over color black, which in turn is preferred over possibly existing other colors. No preferences are specified over those other colors, all are being treated as if they were a single, unspecified, third color. The necessary JOIN operation to join the colors database table is omitted for brevity.

For more examples, refer to M. Galli in [4].

The set of database objects retrieved by a skyline query, called the *skyline* over a database with respect to the provided preferences as defined in [definition 1.2](#), contains only elements which are not *dominated* by other objects, thereby referring to the *dominating* elements as being *interesting*[1]. [Example 1.2](#) shows a skyline over a database's objects. The notion of *dominance* refers to the paradigm of Pareto dominance, i.e., "... given the choice between two objects, with one object being better with respect to at least one attribute but at least equal with respect to all other attributes, users will always prefer the first object over the second one (the first object is said to *dominate* the second one)"[2]. Additionally, C. Lofi *et al.* provide in [2] a tangible example that fits perfectly to this work's real world database's domain of cars (refer to [section 1.3](#)): "...if two car dealers in the neighborhood offer the same model (with same warranties, etc.) at different prices, why should one want to consider the more expensive car?".

Definition 1.2 (Skyline):

The *skyline* set S over a database D with respect to provided preferences over the database's attributes is:

$$S = \{\mathbf{o} \in D \mid \neg \exists \mathbf{p} \in D : \mathbf{p} \succ \mathbf{o}\}.$$

No object must exist that dominates an object in S . Following the terminology in [2], the notion of " $\mathbf{o} \succ \mathbf{p}$ " is interpreted as " \mathbf{o} dominates \mathbf{p} ", or, equivalently, \mathbf{o} is *preferred* over \mathbf{p} ".

Figure 1.1: Dominating objects (i.e., skyline objects) and dominated objects

Example 1.2

Consider figure 1.1. The set $S = \{s_1, \dots, s_4\}$ is the *skyline* over the whole database. The set $P = \{p_1, \dots, p_8\}$ is the set containing the objects *dominated* by objects in S . The whole database is therefore $D = S \cup P$. Note that $S \cap P = \emptyset$.

For example, s_1 *dominates* $\{p_1, p_2\}$ with respect to the preferences specified over the database attributes “price” and “mileage” (both values preferred to be LOW, i.e., following the syntax of [4], specified as “SKYLINE OF price LOW, mileage LOW”). The object p_2 is dominated by the skyline objects $\{s_1, s_2\}$, since both skyline objects are clearly preferred over p_2 with respect to a LOW price and a LOW mileage. It is of no significance whether an object in D is dominated by more than one other object; as soon as it is dominated by at least one other object, it cannot be element in S and therefore becomes an element in P . As shown in definitions 1.1 and 1.2, for each object in S , there is no other object in D that dominates it. On the other hand, for each object in P , there is at least one object in S that dominates it with respect to all preferences specified.

The notion of Pareto dominance is also referred to as being “absolute fair”[2], since only unquestionably dominated database objects are pruned from the reported set of skyline objects. However, the Pareto dominance’s absolute fairness inevitably leads to its major drawbacks: The more preferences specified, a) the bigger the negative impact on the runtime for the skyline calculation and b) the bigger the size of the result set reported by the skyline algorithm. The reason for the growth in size is that most objects are *incomparable* to each other, which in turn is caused by the non-existence of relationships between different attributes as pointed out by C. Lofi *et al.* in [2]. The skyline’s size suffers from the “curse of dimensionality” as introduced by R. Bellman in [5].¹ This quickly leads to result sizes unmanageable for the user when more than

¹Objects within a database become sparse with respect to high dimensions: The more preferences specified and therefore the more dimensions considered for calculating the dominance of one object over another, the more objects become elements of the skyline. Only few objects will be found, at best, which dominate others with

a few preferences are specified. Experiments have shown that already for 5 to 10 preferences, skylines can contain 30% or more objects of the entire database [2]. Presenting a set of this size to the user without sacrificing her user experience is by no means a trivial task.

1.2 Mitigation of Drawbacks

Various approaches, mostly heuristics, have been proposed in order to mitigate the shortcomings mentioned in [section 1.1](#). According to C. Lofi *et al.* in [2], these may be categorized into the following major approaches:

- Relaxation of Pareto dominance
The absolute fairness of the Pareto dominance is weakened, such that less objects are incomparable to others. Such an approach is already implemented in the prefSQL framework in [4], cf. its “OTHERS EQUAL” clause.
- Summarization approaches
These aim to calculate a representative subset of the entire skyline by preserving its statistical characteristics. The *skyline sampling algorithm* (refer to [chapter 2](#) (“[Skyline Sampling](#)”)) examined in this work falls into this category.
- Weighting approaches
At the root of these lies the attempt to numerically quantify the interestingness of objects. This is done by assigning a ranking to the skyline objects, which is investigated in the prefSQL framework in [4], cf. its “RANKING OF” clause.
- Cooperative approaches
These are not heuristics like the other approaches, but rather focus on interacting with the user to draw more information from her, such that queries can be further refined.

This work presents an implementation of the skyline sampling algorithm as introduced by C. Lofi *et al.* in [2] and as proposed in more detail by W.-T. Balke *et al.* in [6] and an integration into the prefSQL framework of M. Galli in [4]. It will be shown that by using this approach, querying a database for a skyline sample is straightforward to the user. The implemented algorithm and relevant subroutines will be shown in pseudo-code and discussed in detail, refer to [chapter 2](#) (“[Skyline Sampling](#)”). Finally, measurement results and observations are discussed and compared to two of the skyline algorithms in the prefSQL framework in [4] (namely, the *BNL* and the *BNLSort* algorithms) and to the properties promised in [6], see [chapter 4](#) (“[Results](#)”).

respect to every single dimension, since as soon as an object is being preferred over a second in only one single dimension, the whole object isn't dominated by the second and remains in the skyline.

1.3 Project Settings

1.3.1 Project Scope

This work is a sub-project of the “Preference-based E-Commerce and Enhanced User Profile Generator (PrefCom)” project², conducted by the Competence Center Distributed Secure Software Systems (D3S)³ at the Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts in cooperation with Arcmedia AG⁴ as industry partner. The project is funded by the Swiss CTI⁵ and the university. PrefCom is concerned with users’ preference-based searches on e-commerce platforms. Prof. Dr. M. Pouly is the project head for PrefCom at the university and is the most important stakeholder for this sub-project in his role as customer. My advisor, Dr. R. Arnold, is a member of PrefCom’s project team. At the project’s kick-off meeting on February 16th 2015, this work’s scope and requirements have been defined, which is resp. are the following:

- Prioritisation of algorithms and approaches in which the user involvement is minimal, at best non-existent, in order to prevent a surge in bounce rates.
- Implementation of the skyline sampling algorithm discussed in [2].
- Integration into the prototypical prefSQL framework in [4], which was constantly under development for the duration of this work, too.
- Integration into the online demonstrators⁶.
- Optimization of the algorithm’s performance with the help of profiling tools.
- Comparison of the results with the promises in [6].
- Adequate incorporation of software engineering practices and principles (e.g., documented source code, unit tests etc.).

M. Galli’s prefSQL framework in [4] is used to provide the user with a means to specify her preferences for an e-commerce application. Her preferences are elicited by certain demonstrators⁶. Since the skyline sampling algorithm is implemented as an addition to the prefSQL framework’s SQL extensions, the integration into the demonstrators, from a user’s perspective, is seamlessly, refer to [section 2.3](#) (“Integration into the prefSQL Framework”).

This work, like the prefSQL framework, benefits greatly from the real world data provided by AutoScout24⁷ which consists of a database containing cars. This is especially important since it turns out that the skyline algorithms as well as the skyline sampling algorithm behave

²<https://www.hslu.ch/en/lucerne-university-of-applied-sciences-and-arts/research/projects/detail/?pid=1015>

³<https://www.hslu.ch/de-ch/technik-architektur/forschung/kompetenzzentren/distributed-secure-software-systems/>

⁴Arcmedia AG, 6003 Lucerne, Switzerland; <http://www.arcmedia.ch/>

⁵The Commission for Technology and Innovation CTI, 3003 Bern, Switzerland; <https://www.kti.admin.ch/kti/en/home.html>

⁶<http://ecom.d3s.ch/>

⁷Scout24 Schweiz AG, AutoScout24, 3175 Flamatt, Switzerland; <http://www.autoscout24.ch/de/auto>

differently for real world data and synthetically generated data, refer to [chapter 4](#) (“Results”). For details about the structure and certain properties of the database, see to [subsection 4.1.3](#) (“AutoScout24 Database”).

1.3.2 Technical Aspects

As desired by the industry partner mentioned in [subsection 1.3.1](#) and necessary for the integration into the existing prefSQL framework in [4], the algorithm described in this report work was implemented in C# with Microsoft’s .NET environment 4.5.1 serving as target platform. The database server used is Microsoft’s SQL Server Enterprise Version 11. Using this product is mandatory in order to deploy C# assemblies as stored procedures.

The prefSQL framework is hosted on GitHub⁸ and is an open-source project under a BSD type license. This work’s implementation is a fork⁹ of the prefSQL framework. However, it has been reintegrated into M. Galli’s main project prefSQL such that as of the time of finishing this work, there is one single, authoritative source for the prefSQL framework, which now includes this work’s skyline sampling algorithm.

The implementation in C# was carried out using Microsoft’s Visual Studio Ultimate 2013 Update 4 IDE together with JetBrains’ Resharper Ultimate 9.1¹⁰ extension. This work’s implementation follows the coding styleguides of the Competence Center Distributed Secure Software Systems (D3S), which were in turn developed during and with the support of this work’s.

The development environment was hosted on virtual machines in the Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts’ Enterprise Lab¹¹.

1.4 Organisation of this Report

First of all, the idea of *skyline sampling* is presented in [chapter 2](#) (“Skyline Sampling”). Moreover, details of the implementation of the skyline sampling algorithm are discussed and the integration in the existing prefSQL framework is shown.

In the following [chapter 3](#) (“Skyline Sample Quality”), the methodology of evaluating the skyline sample’s quality in terms of size and *representativeness* is presented.

The results of the measurements taken are discussed and interpreted in [chapter 4](#) (“Results”). It will be shown under which circumstances the skyline sampling algorithm proves most beneficial

⁸GitHub, Inc.; <https://github.com/>

⁹<https://github.com/taschnue/prefSQL>

¹⁰JetBrains s.r.o.; <https://www.jetbrains.com/resharper/>

¹¹<https://www.enterpriselab.ch/>

and how well it performs compared to other approaches with respect to the metrics considered.

Finally, in [chapter 5](#) (“[Conclusion](#)”), the idea of skyline sampling is critically summarized with respect to the experiments conducted and measurements taken. An outlook is provided about which approaches beyond or besides skyline sampling might promise to be beneficial for future research.

1.5 Acknowledgements

This work has benefited greatly from many discussions and debates among the team of the PrefCom project and the Competence Center D3S as a whole. Of the PrefCom project team, my advisor Dr. R. Arnold, Prof. Dr. M. Pouly, M. Galli and R. Christen have all been most helpful with various insights, discussions, recommendations and suggestions. Besides, discussing statistical aspects with Prof. Dr. J. Bürgler and P. Buchter has proved supportive for this work.

Chapter 2

Skyline Sampling

2.1 Idea and Background

The *skyline sampling algorithm* is a heuristic approach proposed by W.-T. Balke *et al.* in [6]. By its application, the absolute fairness of the paradigm of Pareto dominance as illustrated in [chapter 1](#) (“[Introduction](#)”) is weakened. In return, this provides for attacking the skyline algorithms’ major shortcomings in terms of excessive runtime and result sets of unmanageable size while still maintaining the properties of the entire Pareto dominance’s skyline to a certain degree. In particular, the properties to uphold or to improve are [6]:

- All objects dominated within the set of the entire database are still to be *eliminated* in the skyline sample, just as they are when calculating the entire skyline. I.e., the notion of a customer *always preferring* one product over another which is clearly worse (e.g., over a more expensive product offering no other benefits) has still to be respected.
- The *runtime* to build and report the skyline sample has to be *practical*, i.e., mustn’t exceed two seconds in order to be useful for e-commerce applications to minimize bounce rates. This is especially a challenge for the calculation of the entire skyline via one of the algorithms implemented in the prefSQL framework in [4] when the number of specified preferences increases.
- The *size* of the skyline sample has to be *manageable*, i.e., only a fraction of the whole database should be reported. The entire skyline may easily contain 30% and more of the whole database as mentioned in [2].
- Any subset of the entire skyline, such as the skyline sample calculated by this algorithm, should be *as representative as possible* for the entire skyline. This ensures that the user is presented a result as unbiased as possible in order to preserve the entire skyline’s characteristics.

The main idea of the algorithm is to prevent the calculation of a high-dimensional skyline with many preferences for the reasons described in [chapter 1](#) (“Introduction”). Instead, a certain amount of *subset skylines* is calculated, which are themselves skylines - in the sense of Pareto dominance - of a lower dimensionality, i.e., of only a subset of all preferences specified. Since these low-dimensional subset skylines respect only few preferences, they may be looked upon as a representation of a *topic of interest*, i.e., they provide for a specific vantage point, a specific perspective, on the entire skyline and therefore the whole database over all of the user’s preferences.

The objects within these subset skylines are afterwards compared with each other in order to eliminate objects which are dominated with respect to the entire, high-dimensional skyline. Finally, the union of the database objects contained in the subset skylines are reported as the *skyline sample*. The calculation of the subset skylines is delegated to prefSQL’s existing skyline algorithms. [Algorithm 2.1](#) shows this process in more detail and is discussed in [section 2.2](#).

W.-T. Balke *et al.* suggest in [\[6\]](#) as well as in a personal communication that the skyline sampling approach should be understood as a preliminary step only to get an early impression of the entire skyline. The skyline sample should subsequently be presented to the user to elicit her feedback on the sample. She provides this feedback by choosing a few objects she is interested in. With this additional information, the “most adequate weightings for subsequent focused top k retrieval”[\[6\]](#) are derived.

However, as discussed in [section 1.3](#) (“Project Settings”), the main project’s goal is to keep the user from having to provide information over and over again as much as possible. This is why the second aspect of the algorithm as proposed in [\[6\]](#), eliciting user’s feedback with subsequent calculations, is not covered by this work. Nevertheless, even the calculation of the skyline sample alone shows promising results with regard to the aforementioned properties which are to be upheld or improved.

2.2 The Skyline Sampling Algorithm

In order to prevent the calculation of a high-dimensional skyline, a number of subset skylines is calculated instead, each of a low dimensionality. With this approach, both major shortcomings of the Pareto dominance skyline are mitigated: Skylines of low dimensionality can usually be calculated fast and consist of fewer database objects than a high-dimensional skyline. The subset skylines are calculated with exactly the same properties as the entire, high-dimensional skyline.

In fact, the implementation of the skyline sampling algorithm developed in this work delegates the calculation of the necessary subset skylines to the already existing skyline algorithms of the prefSQL framework in [\[4\]](#), which have been altered in two ways: a) the skyline algorithms don’t have to query the database server for each subset skyline which would be the case without the modifications of this work’s implementation; the database query is executed only once, and

b) preferences which are to be ignored for a subset skyline can be specified with an “ignore” attribute when calling the skyline algorithm, refer to [section 2.3](#) for details. As a result, the overall performance of the skyline sampling algorithm could be improved such that it mainly depends on the performance of the underlying skyline algorithms and therefore, in general, introduces only a small overhead, refer to e.g. [section 4.3](#) (“Practicable Runtime”).

The decision of which subsets to choose from the set of the user’s preferences is made randomly, based on two properties serving as input to the algorithm:

1. The number q of subset skylines to be calculated. This is specified in the COUNT element of this work’s addition to the prefSQL syntax¹².
2. The dimension m of the subset for the skylines. This is specified in the DIMENSION element of this work’s addition to the prefSQL¹².

However, the values assigned to m and q are not independent of each other, and both in turn depend on the number n of preferences specified over the entire database’s attributes:

- Each of the n preferences has to be included in at least one of the q subsets. Otherwise, certain preferences would be disregarded completely which would disagree with the user’s request.
- No subset combining the same preferences should be included more than once. Since finally a union of all of the subset skylines is created, calculating the same subset skyline more than once would be meaningless.

Hence, the restrictions for specifying m and q are those provided in [equations \(2.1\)](#) and [\(2.2\)](#). P is the set of preferences specified over a database’s attributes, q is the number of subsets, m is the dimension of each subset, P_{sample} is the set of all subsets of P over which subset skylines should be calculated.

$$m \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \wedge m \cdot q \geq n \wedge q \leq \binom{n}{m} \quad (2.1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} |P| &= n \\ P_{sample} &\subset 2^P, |P_{sample}| = q \\ \forall P_{sub} \in P_{sample} : |P_{sub}| &= m, P_{sub} \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}^m \\ \forall p \in P : \exists P_{sub} \in P_{sample} : p &\in P_{sub} \end{aligned} \quad (2.2)$$

After a subset skyline has been calculated according to the paradigm of Pareto dominance with respect to the low-dimensional subset, it is necessary to examine the subset skyline for objects which are dominated with respect to the *entire, high-dimensional* skyline. As stated

¹²e.g., “SKYLINE OF ... SAMPLE BY RANDOM_SUBSETS COUNT q DIMENSION m ”

in [section 2.1](#), the resulting skyline sample mustn't contain dominated objects, i.e., the skyline sample has to be a subset of the entire skyline. Hence, the subset skylines cannot simply be merged, but have to be examined for dominated objects. This is discussed in [subsection 2.2.1](#).

Finally, the union of the elements of the subset skylines is created and is finally reported as the result of the skyline sampling algorithm, the skyline sample.

[Algorithm 2.1](#) shows the steps described in this section in detail.

Algorithm 2.1 Skyline Sampling

Input:

$P \leftarrow$ preferences specified over a database's attributes. $|P| = n$.
 $q \leftarrow$ number of subsets.
 $m \leftarrow$ dimension of each subset.

Output:

S_{sample} : The skyline sample set of database objects.

- 1: $D \leftarrow$ entire database from SQL server. /* via ANSI SQL query */
- 2: $S_{sample} \leftarrow \emptyset$ (S_{sample} is constructed incrementally to finally contain the skyline sample).
- 3: $P_{sample} \leftarrow$ randomly selected subsets honouring the constraints in [equation \(2.2\)](#).
- 4: **for all** $P_{sub} \in P_{sample}$ **do** /* $|P_{sub}| = m$ */
- 5: Sort D in ascending order over each element's subset dimension.
- 6: $S_{sub} \leftarrow$ subset skyline of dimension m over database D over preferences P_{sub} , calculated by a skyline algorithm of the prefSQL framework. $S_{sub} \subseteq D$.
- 7: $E_{all} \leftarrow$ GETOBJECTSWITHEQUALVALUE(S_{sub})
- 8: **for all** $E \in E_{all}$ **do** /* $E \subseteq S_{sub}$ */
- 9: $P'_{sub} \leftarrow P \setminus P_{sub}$ /* P'_{sub} is the subset's complement with respect to P . */
- 10: $S'_{sub} \leftarrow$ subset skyline of dimension $n - m$ of database E over preferences P'_{sub} , calculated by a skyline algorithm of the prefSQL framework.
- 11: $S_{sub} \leftarrow S_{sub} \setminus (E \setminus S'_{sub})$ /* remove objects dominated with respect to P'_{sub} */
- 12: $S_{sample} \leftarrow S_{sample} \cup S_{sub}$
- 13: Sort S_{sample} according to *BEST_RANK()* or *SUM_RANK()* clause.
- 14: Remove objects from S_{sample} according to *TOP* clause.
- 15: **return** S_{sample}

2.2.1 Elimination of Dominated Subset Skyline Objects

As mentioned in [section 2.2](#), the objects reported in a subset skyline have to be checked whether they are dominated with respect to the entire, high-dimensional skyline.

Therefore, all objects of a subset skyline are compared with each other. Objects with equal values with respect to the low-dimensional subset's preferences have to be examined for dominance. Only objects with equal values might be dominated with respect to the entire, high-dimensional skyline, since all objects with worse values have already been discarded because they're dominated with respect to the low-dimensional subset preferences. If such objects with equal values are found, *another subset skyline is calculated* over these with respect to the subset S 's relative complement with respect to the entire set of preferences P , i.e., $P \setminus S$.

Objects not contained in the subset's complement skyline are discarded from the subset skyline. This is illustrated in [example 2.1](#). W.-T. Balke *et al.* [6] have proven that afterwards, no dominated object can possibly remain in the subset skyline. Note that it is not necessary to calculate the entire skyline to decide whether objects are dominated within the subset skyline, but merely the objects in the reported subset skyline may have to be processed.

In [algorithm 2.2](#) (“Get Objects with Equal Value”), the subset skyline is examined in order to extract all database objects which consist of equal values with respect to the subset reported by the skyline algorithm. For each *bucket*, i.e., unique combination of such values, a list of the objects assigned to this bucket is created and reported. Refer to [example 2.2](#) for the desired results.

Algorithm 2.2 Get Objects with Equal Value

Input: $S_{sub} \leftarrow$ subset skyline.

Output: E_{all} : All objects with the same value. $\forall E \in E_{all} : E \subseteq S_{sub}$.

```

1: Sequence  $D \leftarrow S_{sub}$ .
2: Sort  $D$  in ascending order over each element's first subset dimension.
3: Sequence  $C \leftarrow$  a copy of  $D$ .
4:  $E_{all} \leftarrow \emptyset$ . /* Contains sets; each of these sets contains objects of  $S_{sub}$  with equal values */
5: for all  $d \in D$  do
6:   Sequence  $C_{next} \leftarrow ()$ .
7:   for all  $c \in C$  do
8:     if  $c = d$  then /* prevent comparison of same object */
9:       continue loop on  $c \in C$ .
10:    if  $c_0 > d_0$  then /* 0 is the ordered subset dimension */
11:      Add  $c$  and all elements of  $C$  not yet visited in this  $d$ 's iteration to  $C_{next}$ .
12:      break loop on  $c \in C$ .
13:    /* From here on, it is ensured that  $c_0 = d_0$ . */
14:    for  $i \leftarrow 1, |c| - 1$  do
15:      if  $c_i \neq d_i$  then
16:        Add  $c$  to  $C_{next}$ .
17:        continue loop on  $c \in C$ .
18:    /* From here on, it is ensured that  $\forall i \in \{0, 1, \dots, |c| - 1\} : c_i = d_i$ . */
19:     $v \leftarrow$  bucket of  $c$ . /*  $v$  is the bucket chosen by a combined, unique hash over the
    values of each  $c_i$  to which  $\{c, d\}$  have to be added. */
20:    if  $E_v \notin E_{all}$  then
21:       $E_v \leftarrow \emptyset$ .
22:       $E_v \leftarrow E_v \cup \{c, d\}$ .
23:       $E_{all} \leftarrow E_{all} \cup E_v$ .
24:     $C \leftarrow C_{next}$ .
25:    if  $|C| = 0$  then
26:      break loop on  $d \in D$ .
27: return  $E_{all}$ .

```

Figure 2.1: Subset skyline over the preference “price” only

Example 2.1

Consider figure 1.1. Note that p_8 is dominated by s_4 , since they’re indeed equal with respect to the price, but s_4 has a lower mileage. Hence, s_4 dominates p_8 , which goes along with definitions 1.1 and 1.2.

Now consider figure 2.1. This shows the skyline over a *subset* of the preferences “price” and “mileage”, namely, only the subset skyline over the “price”. Now, s_2 mustn’t be part of the final skyline sample, because, with respect to the *entire, high-dimensional* skyline (i.e., with respect to the preferences “price” and “mileage”), s_2 is *dominated* by s_1 . But, as stated in section 2.1, the skyline sample mustn’t contain such objects.

Hence, every object of the subset skyline has to be compared to each other in order to find those with the same price, which in this example’s case, is $\{s_1, s_2\}$. These objects have to be investigated whether they dominate each other with respect to the subset’s relative complement with respect to the entire set of preferences, i.e., with respect to “mileage”. Now, clearly, s_1 dominates s_2 . Therefore, s_2 is removed from the subset skyline, and only the remaining set $\{s_1\}$ is merged into the final skyline sample, which is perfectly fine, since s_1 is an element in the entire, high-dimensional skyline, too.

Note that with respect to only one dimension, there can be only one set of the same equal values. However, this is not true for more than one dimension; consider figure 1.1, which could in turn be a subset skyline of two preferences “price” and “mileage” with an imaginary entire skyline of more preferences. In figure 1.1, there are four sets of objects of the same values, namely $\{s_1\}$, $\{s_2\}$, $\{s_3\}$ and $\{s_4\}$.

Example 2.2

This shows the desired results of [algorithm 2.2](#) for a set of 7 subset skyline database objects. A bucket value of “-” signals that the subset’s values for this object are unique, i.e., there’s no need to process this object as discussed in [subsection 2.2.1](#).

Object's unique ID	value preference #1	value preference #2	value preference #3	Bucket
1	1	2	3	-
2	1	2	4	1
3	3	4	5	2
4	1	2	4	1
5	4	2	1	-
6	1	2	4	1
7	3	4	5	2

Table 2.1: Example of a set of 7 subset skyline database objects. The subset’s dimension is 3, hence 3 preferences are shown together with their assigned bucket.

Even though theoretically, each object would have to be compared to each other, resulting in a runtime complexity of $O(n^2)$, a practical runtime of about $O(n)$ is achieved by [algorithm 2.2](#) as experiments have shown. The reasons for this are the following:

- The subset skyline is *sorted* on the first column before the algorithm is carried out. Hence, the comparison on [line 10](#) (“[Get Objects with Equal Value](#)”) skips many unnecessary comparisons for subsequent columns.
- Objects which have been found to be equal are *excluded* from future comparisons, again reducing the number of necessary loops. As shown on [line 16](#) (“[Get Objects with Equal Value](#)”), an object is only included in the following outer loop’s comparisons if it has not been equal to the outer object.

The if-clause in [line 10](#) (“[Get Objects with Equal Value](#)”) tests whether subsequent elements in C have to be tested at all against the outer iteration’s current d . Since both C and D are ordered by the first subset dimension, if the current c_0 is larger than the current d_0 , the first subset dimension of every subsequent element in C will also be larger. Thus, comparisons with the rest of C with the current d are superfluous, and the algorithm therefore breaks out of the inner iteration. An example run of this algorithm is illustrated in [example 2.3](#).

Example 2.3

Example of iterations in [table 2.3](#) for the objects shown in [table 2.2](#) within [algorithm 2.2](#) (“Get Objects with Equal Value”). As discussed in [subsection 2.2.1](#), the number of iterations is not $7^2 = 49$ (compare with each other), but merely 13, which is indeed about $\in O(n)$.

	Object’s unique ID						
Value preference #1, ordered in ascending order, refer to line 2 (“Get Objects with Equal Value”)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Value preference #2	1	1	1	3	3	3	3
	2	1	2	4	4	1	4

Table 2.2: Example objects of a subset skyline to be compared for equality

Outer iteration #	Inner iteration #	d 's ID (outer iteration)	c 's ID (outer iteration)	$c \stackrel{?}{=} d$	d_0 (preference #1)	c_0 (preference #1)	$c_0 \stackrel{?}{>} d_0$	d_1 (preference #2)	c_1 (preference #2)	$c_1 \stackrel{?}{=} d_1$	C_{next}	E_{call}
1	1	1	1	T	- ^a	-	-	-	-	-	$()^b$	\emptyset
1	2	1	2	F	1	1	F	2	1	F	$(2)^c$	\emptyset
1	3	1	3	F	1	1	F	2	2	T	$(2)^d$	$\{\{1, 3\}\}$
1	4	1	4	F	1	3	T	-	-	-	$(2,4-7)^e$	$\{\{1, 3\}\}$
2	1	2	2	T	-	-	-	-	-	-	$()$	$\{\{1, 3\}\}$
2	2	2	4	F	1	3	T	-	-	-	$(4-7)$	$\{\{1, 3\}\}$
3	1	3	4	F	1	3	T	-	-	-	$(4-7)$	$\{\{1, 3\}\}$
4	1	4	4	T	-	-	-	-	-	-	$()$	$\{\{1, 3\}\}$
4	2	4	5	F	3	3	F	4	4	T	$()$	$\{\{1, 3\}, \{4, 5\}\}$
4	3	4	6	F	3	3	F	4	1	F	(6)	$\{\{1, 3\}, \{4, 5\}\}$
4	4	4	7	F	3	3	F	4	4	T	(6)	$\{\{1, 3\}, \{4, 5, 7\}\}$
5	1	5	6	F	3	3	F	4	1	F	(6)	$\{\{1, 3\}, \{4, 5, 7\}\}$
6	1	6	6	T	-	-	-	-	-	-	$()$	$\{\{1, 3\}, \{4, 5, 7\}\}$

Table 2.3: Example iterations for [algorithm 2.2](#) (“Get Objects with Equal Value”)

^athroughout the table, “-” means “not determined in the current iteration”.

^b c and d are the same objects, skip to next iteration of inner loop ([line 8](#)).

^c c is not equal to d with respect to all subset dimensions; hence, it remains to be evaluated in forthcoming iterations whether an object with the same values exists. Hence, add to C_{next} for next outer iteration’s step according to [line 16](#).

^d c is not added, since it is already equal to another element and therefore added into a bucket together with d . [Line 16](#) will not be executed. Break the inner loop.

^e c_i and all following $c' \in Comp$ are larger with respect to the first subset dimension; add to list for next outer iteration’s step according to [line 10](#).

The algorithm was not implemented to support parallelised execution of certain regions of the algorithm. However, this might prove beneficial in future research, since the calculations of the subset skylines are completely independent from each other, such that it is expectable to reduce the runtime even more, refer to [chapter 5](#) (“Conclusion”).

In a prior work to [6], namely [7], W.-T. Balke *et al.* suggest that for the sake of minimizing runtime, the comparisons discussed in this section could be omitted and the requirement of the sample containing only objects which are dominated with respect to the entire skyline could be dropped (refer to [section 2.1](#)). Indeed, these comparisons consume some of the runtime.

However, as [section 4.3](#) (“Practicable Runtime”) shows, those comparisons are only a small fraction of the whole skyline sampling algorithm’s runtime. Additionally, the skyline sample would grow in size, which is the other main reason besides minimizing runtime the whole sampling approach is considered in the first place.

But most important of all might be the implications from a user’s perspective. All that is known as input from the user are her specified preferences. If these are no longer respected, or even only weakened, such that objects are returned that are clearly dominated, this behaviour might well jeopardize the user’s willingness to interact with the application as a whole. Clearly, this is highly prohibitive. Additionally, as discussed in [chapter 3](#) (“Skyline Sample Quality”), the information available from the user, her preferences, are already scarce to begin with when it comes to deciding what is a *good*, a *representative*, sample justifiably to return to her. If this information is weakened, the assessment of the skyline sample’s quality becomes even harder.

2.3 Integration into the prefSQL Framework

The integration of the skyline sampling algorithm into the existing prefSQL framework in [4] is straightforward from a user’s perspective. The interface of prefSQL is extended by a simple clause:

```
SAMPLE BY RANDOM_SUBSETS COUNT  $q$  DIMENSION  $m$ 
```

This extension has been included seamlessly in the existing ANTLR¹³ parser used in [4]. The supplied parameters q and m must honour the restrictions in [equation \(2.1\)](#). Otherwise, an exception is thrown.

The syntax “SAMPLE BY RANDOM_SUBSETS” was chosen in order to allow for potential future extensions, as it may well be that the implemented sampling method of the skyline sampling algorithm is not optimal for certain requirements and other approaches should be integrated. Even in the early stages of this work, it has been investigated whether it might prove

¹³<http://www.antlr.org/>

Figure 2.2: Architecture of the prefSQL framework

beneficial if an influence could be exerted on what subsets the subset skylines should be calculated upon. As of now, in conformity with what W.-T. Balke *et al.* suggest in [6], those subsets are chosen randomly from the set of all the user’s preferences. However, e.g., future research might reveal that if a user values some preferences more than on others, it may prove beneficial if the higher valued preferences appeared in more subsets. Hence, an extension of the syntax could provide for specifying explicit subsets to calculate the subset skylines, which might manifest in specifying “SAMPLE BY SUBSETS (price, mileage), (price, color), (price, horsepower)”. But investigating this or similar approaches in detail was out of scope for this work, this is just to provide a sketch of one possible future extension.

When it came to deciding how to integrate the skyline sampling algorithm into the existing code of the prefSQL framework in [4], it turned out that this could be done in several ways.

The workflow of the prefSQL framework is depicted in figure 2.2. The regions “Client” and “MS CLR” refer to different tiers the framework can run on. The region “SQLCommon” contains the prefSQL library, providing its public interface via the SQLCommon class, which may be included as dependency in a client’s project. Then, all the code runs on the client’s tier, and all the data of the database is fetched from the database’s tier (which of course may coincide

with the client's tier). The other possibility to integrate the prefSQL framework is to deploy an assembly of stored procedures into an MSSQL server, the client's tier calling those stored procedures. Therefore, only the resulting skyline is transferred from the database's tier to the client's tier, not the whole database, which will reduce network traffic if the tiers are physically separated. For more detail on the prefSQL framework and its integration, refer to M. Galli in [4].

In figures 2.2 to 2.6, the shaded areas try to account for the two possible approaches (either run the skyline algorithm on the client's tier or on the database's tier); This is the very the same artefact, the prefSQL .NET assembly, either a) used together with the client application as its dependency or b) deployed stand-alone into the MSSQL server. Either the client executes the whole skyline algorithm from its own tier and receives the resulting skyline, or it queries the prefSQL framework to *convert* the prefSQL statement containing the clause "SKYLINE OF ..." into an ANSI SQL string containing the call to a stored procedure and executes this ANSI SQL query via an arbitrary database connection to a server into which the assembly providing the stored procedures has been deployed. Again, for more detail, refer to [4]. These two ways are mainly provided for different use cases for end customers - it may well be that the deployment of the assembly onto an MSSQL server is not allowed, such that the algorithm has to be performed on some separate application server.

Now, with this architecture, additional skyline algorithms can be easily integrated. However, this is not the case for the skyline *sampling* algorithm, since it is not a replacement for a skyline algorithm, but resides, figuratively speaking, one level "above" the skyline algorithms. The skyline sampling algorithm re-uses the skyline algorithms in order to calculate the necessary subset skylines, removes certain objects from them and reports their union (for more detail, refer to section 2.2). The user's preferences have therefore to be preprocessed and cannot be used to directly calculate the samples.

Now, the prefSQL statement containing the clause "SKYLINE OF ..." is parsed into C# classes via ANTLR. These classes represent the user's preferences among other things. Since these classes are *private* to the prefSQL framework, they couldn't be accessed by the skyline sampling algorithm without refactoring the existing code.

In the following, certain integration possibilities that were discussed during this work are depicted in figures 2.3 to 2.6 and evaluated with respect to certain criteria in tables 2.4 to 2.7.

Figure 2.4: Integration variant “PrefSQLModel”

- Exhibit currently internal-only PrefSQLModel
- Refactor current interface (parsePreferenceSQL and parseAndExecutePrefSQL) to smaller and accessible methods
- Build Sample Skyline queries based on the PrefSQLModel resulting from ANTLR parsing (as it is done already in order to generate the ANSI SQL string)
- Re-combine the single preferences according to the given SAMPLE BY parameters
- Do all of this in the client’s tier, existing stored procedures are unaffected

Risk for prefSQL:	0	(refactoring)
Risk for SkylineSampling:	0	(build SQL from Model)
Maintainability:	+	(based on grammar)
Framework Consistency:	-	(no parsePrefSQL)
Refactoring effort:	+	(local refactoring)
Implementation effort:	+	(build SQL from Model)

Table 2.5: Evaluation of variant “PrefSQLModel”

Figure 2.5: Integration variant “Skyline sampling stored procedure”

- Introduce distinct Skyline Sampling stored procedure
- Use this stored procedure as entry point for all Skyline Sampling tasks
- Add necessary parameters COUNT and DIMENSION without the need of extending parameters of existing stored procedures
- Create subsets of the preferences via Regex-Splitting

Risk for prefSQL:	++	(no modifications)
Risk for SkylineSampling:	-	(Regex, CLR)
Maintainability:	--	(Regex complexity)
Framework Consistency:	++	(no modifications)
Refactoring effort:	++	(no modifications)
Implementation effort:	0	(Regex complexity)

Table 2.6: Evaluation of variant “Skyline sampling stored procedure”

Figure 2.6: Integration variant “Master stored procedure”

- Rework current interface to single stored procedures by wrapping around a single master stored procedure
- This stored procedure would accept two parameters only: the original
- Preference SQL string and the Skyline algorithm chosen (no matter whether Skyline Sampling is required or not)
- ANTLR parsing is done within the stored procedure, client tier becomes thin

Risk for prefSQL:	- -	(big refactoring, CLR)
Risk for SkylineSampling:	-	(Regex, CLR)
Maintainability:	++	(consistent logic)
Framework Consistency:	++	(only Preference SQL)
Refactoring effort:	- -	(big refactoring)
Implementation effort:	- -	(big refactoring)

Table 2.7: Evaluation of variant “Master stored procedure”

The variant “skyline sampling stored procedure” (refer to [figure 2.5](#)) has been chosen to be implemented. Hence, the skyline sampling algorithm can be used similar to the other skyline algorithms, either by execution on the client’s tier or on the database’s tier. To mitigate the major drawback of the Regex-Splittings, the interface to the existing skyline algorithms has been altered such that they now provide for a means to ignore certain preferences, this has been mentioned beforehand in [section 2.2](#). The preferences were already passed as a string to the skyline algorithms, e.g., "LOW;LOW;LOW;LOW" for four preferences. Some construct like this is inevitable, since the stored procedures on the database server can accept only values of scalar type and not complex objects. If a subset of these is chosen, the skyline sampling algorithm passes a string like "LOW;LOW;IGNORE;LOW" when a subset skyline of the subset of the first, the second and the fourth preference is to be calculated. Refer to [example 2.4](#) for an illustration of this. Moreover, this approach provides for the ability to use the same, only once retrieved database for all subsequent subset skyline calculations, since the database structure remains the same even for subset skylines and can therefore be easily merged in the end.

Example 2.4

Assume that a prefSQL statement containing certain user preferences is specified like this:

```
SELECT cs.id, cs.price, cs.mileage, colors.name FROM cars cs LEFT OUTER JOIN
colors ON cs.color_id = colors.ID SKYLINE OF cs.price LOW, cs.mileage LOW, col-
ors.name ('red' » 'blue' » OTHERS EQUAL);
```

This gets translated by the prefSQL framework in [4] to the following ANSI SQL statement when using the BNL algorithm:

```
EXEC dbo.SP_SkylineBNLLevel 'SELECT CAST(cs.price AS bigint) AS SkylineAt-
tribute0, CAST(cs.mileage AS bigint) AS SkylineAttribute1, CAST(CASE WHEN
colors.name = "red" THEN 0 WHEN colors.name = "blue" THEN 100 ELSE 200 END AS
bigint) AS SkylineAttribute2, cs.id, cs.price, cs.mileage, colors.name FROM cars cs LEFT
OUTER JOIN colors ON cs.color_id = colors.ID', 'LOW;LOW;LOW', 0, 0;
```

Now, the skyline sampling algorithm could perform some Regex-Splittings on the selected attributes (“CAST(cs.price AS bigint) AS SkylineAttribute0” and so on). This is error-prone, makes maintainability harder and is therefore prohibitive. Hence, a replacement of the parameter “LOW;LOW;LOW” passed to the stored procedure is performed. If a subset skyline over just the first two attributes is to be calculated, this parameter simply becomes “LOW;LOW;IGNORE” in order to indicate to the skyline algorithm to just consult the first two attributes when deciding which objects dominate others.

The skyline algorithms “BNL” and “BNLSort” have been adapted to this behaviour. The other skyline algorithms of the prefSQL framework, “Divide and Conquer” and “Hexagon”, have not been altered since at the time of this work, their usefulness seemed restricted by either

needing too much memory or exhibiting prohibitive runtime.

The native SQL algorithm which maps the preference SQL statement into a huge ANSI SQL statement containing a lot of `WHERE`-clauses has not been prepared for the skyline sampling approach, since this would complicate the ANSI SQL statement even more. Aside from that, future research would have to show if the skyline sampling approach is translatable to ANSI SQL at all.

Chapter 3

Skyline Sample Quality

As discussed in [section 2.1](#) (“[Idea and Background](#)”), the skyline sample calculated has to ensure certain properties. The first of them, that it contains no objects which would be dominated with respect to the entire, high-dimensional skyline, has already been discussed in [chapter 2](#) (“[Skyline Sampling](#)”) and was proven by W.-T. Balke *et al.* in [\[6\]](#). This chapter elaborates on the representativeness of the skyline sample calculated. The practical runtime and the manageability of its site is investigated directly in [chapter 4](#) (“[Results](#)”).

It is not straightforward to come up with criteria on how to evaluate the quality, the representativeness, of the skyline sample. This is rooted in the scarce information available: Only the user’s preferences can be used as input, and this input is already exploited in calculating the entire skyline. It may well be argued that calculating subset skylines provide for certain perspectives on the entire skyline, for topics of interest providing a narrower view, although the possibilities for choosing those subsets are vast, as will be shown in [chapter 4](#). Nevertheless, research has come up with certain ideas on how to objectify the quality of a subset of an entire skyline, some of them are used in this work in order to provide an estimation of the quality of the skyline sampling algorithm as a whole.

All but the method described in [section 3.3](#) (“[Dominated Objects](#)”) use not the skyline attributes’ values as calculated by the underlying skyline algorithm, but rather operate on normalized data. Each skyline attribute is normalized according to [equation \(3.1\)](#), where $d \in \mathbb{N}$ is the dimension of the skyline S , i.e. the number of skyline attributes, i.e. the number of columns over which preferences have been specified. [Equation \(3.1\)](#) ensures that $s'_i \in [0, 1] \subset \mathbb{R}$.

$$\forall s \in S, \forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, d\} : s'_i = \frac{s_i - \min_{t \in S} t_i}{\max_{t \in S} t_i - \min_{t \in S} t_i}. \quad (3.1)$$

Some measurements require comparisons with the entire skyline. However, the calculation of

the entire skyline is only needed for taking measurements to evaluate the quality of the skyline sample and is not part of the actual skyline sampling algorithm. This is worth pointing out explicitly, since as discussed in [chapter 1](#) (“Introduction”), the calculation of the entire skyline is often prohibitive with respect to the runtime.

3.1 Set Coverage

The idea of *set coverage* used in this work is proposed by W.-T. Balke *et al.* in [6]. In [definition 3.1](#), it is rephrased in order to correspond to the terminology used in this work. The calculation of the set coverage is illustrated in [examples 3.1](#) and [3.2](#).

Definition 3.1 (Set Coverage):

Let S be the set of database objects in the entire skyline with each object’s column values normalized according to [equation \(3.1\)](#). Let $T, U \subseteq S$, $|T| = |U|$.^a

For each $t \in T$, determine an object $u \in U$, such that their Euclidean distance $\|t, u\|$ is minimized.

This object u is *assigned* to the object t , i.e., u is *covered* by t . The *set coverage* of T over U is the percentage of database objects in U that have been assigned to / are covered by objects in T .

^a[6] specify $|T| \sim |U|$. However, in this work’s implementation, sets of equal cardinality are examined.

Example 3.1

Suppose that the objects in [table 3.1](#) are reported by a skyline query. The object's values have been normalized according to [equation \(3.1\)](#).

Object's unique ID	1	2	3	4	5	6
Object's value ^a	0.1	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.8	1.0

Table 3.1: Objects to be investigated with respect to set coverage

As described in [definition 3.1](#) (“Set Coverage”), two subsets of the entire skyline of equal cardinality are extracted and shown in [tables 3.2](#) and [3.3](#).

Object's unique ID	1	3	5
Object's value	0.1	0.4	0.8

Table 3.2: Random subset U to be covered by set T

Object's unique ID	1	4	6
Object's value	0.1	0.5	1.0

Table 3.3: Set T covering set U

Now, each $t \in T$ is assigned a $u \in U$ with respect to their minimal Euclidean distance, as shown in [table 3.4](#).

Object's value	$u = 0.1$	$u = 0.4$	$u = 0.8$
$t = 0.1$	0.0	0.3	0.7
$t = 0.5$	0.4	0.1	0.3
$t = 1.01$	0.9	0.6	0.2

Table 3.4: Euclidean distances between objects in order to determine the set coverage

The percentage of objects in U assigned to / covered by objects in T , i.e., the set coverage of T over U , is **100%**.

^afor brevity, only one dimension is used in this example; however, since the Euclidean distance can be calculated without difficulties over an arbitrary number of dimensions, adding more dimensions would just add to the complexity of this example without providing additional insight.

Example 3.2

The skyline objects and the set U are the same as in [example 3.1](#). However, set T consists of the objects shown in [table 3.5](#). The only difference is that instead of object Id 4, object Id 5 is picked.

Object's unique ID	1	5	6
Object's value	0.1	0.8	1.0

Table 3.5: Another set T covering set U

As in [example 3.1](#), each $t \in T$ is assigned a $u \in U$ with respect to their minimal Euclidean distance, as shown in [table 3.6](#).

Object's value	$u = 0.1$	$u = 0.4$	$u = 0.8$
$t = 0.1$	0.0	0.3	0.7
$t = 0.8$	0.7	0.4	0.0
$t = 1.01$	0.9	0.6	0.2

Table 3.6: Euclidean distances between objects in order to determine the set coverage

The percentage of objects in U assigned to / covered by objects in T , i.e., the set coverage of T over U , is **66%**. Two objects in T (Id 5 and 6) are covering one object in U (Id 5), and object Id 3 is not covered by any $t \in T$ at all.

The set coverage is used as a measurement to evaluate the quality of a skyline sample T . Its elements are evaluated against a randomly chosen subset U of the entire skyline of the same cardinality. The percentage of objects covered in the random subset is the skyline sample's set coverage. This procedure is described in [algorithm 3.1](#).

Algorithm 3.1 SetCoverage

Input: T, U containing database objects, normalized according to [equation \(3.1\)](#), $|T| = |U|$.

Output: Set coverage of T over U in percent.

- 1: $A \leftarrow \emptyset$. /* A contains all elements in T assigned to an element in U */
- 2: **for all** $t \in T$ **do**
- 3: $u_{min} \leftarrow \min_{u \in U} \|t, u\|$
- 4: $A \leftarrow A \cup \{u_{min}\}$
- 5: **return** $|A| / |U|$

A “good”, realistic value for the set coverage is not easily obtained. A value of 100% might appear desirable. However, that would mean that each element in the skyline sample has a corresponding element in the randomly chosen subset of the entire skyline that is very “near” to it - and only it - with respect to the Euclidean distance. This will almost never happen, not even with randomly generated synthetic data, since the set tested for coverage is chosen randomly.

Therefore, a better comparison can be obtained if another randomly chosen subset of the entire skyline of the same cardinality is tested for coverage against the first created random subset. Calculating the set coverage of two random subsets introduces an unbiased calibration value which is supposed to be *representative* for the entire skyline. The set coverage of the skyline sample can be compared to this “fairly” determined coverage and should be “similar” to it. If this is the case, the skyline sample is considered to *represent* the entire skyline in a meaningful way with respect to the metric of set coverage.

Calculating the set coverage for different random subsets and taking their average may seem desirable in order to compensate for the arbitrarily chosen random objects. Nevertheless, experiments have shown that this makes little to no difference for the percentage calculated, but instead takes a lot of runtime. Hence, only one random subset is taken and compared.

3.2 Cluster Analysis

Just like the idea of set coverage presented in [section 3.1](#), performing a *cluster analysis* is proposed by W.-T. Balke *et al.* in [\[6\]](#). It aims to investigate the distribution of a skyline sample’s objects over the database’s attributes’ space. By comparing the histograms of the distributions of the skyline sample’s objects and those of the entire skyline, a measurement is obtained on how well the skyline sample represents the entire skyline.

To render this comprehensible, the normalized database objects of the skyline sample are assigned a *bucket* according to [definition 3.2](#). “The bucket assigned gives a rough idea where objects are located in n -dimensional space.”[\[6\]](#)

Definition 3.2 (Buckets for Cluster Analysis):

Let S be the set of database objects in the skyline sample with each object’s column values normalized according to [equation \(3.1\)](#)

Each dimension of the skyline S , i.e. each skyline attributes, i.e. each column over which a preference has been specified, is divided into an “upper” and a “lower” partition.^a

With respect to these two partitions, each object is reduced to a value in $\{0, 1, \dots, 2^d\}$ with d being the number of attributes of a database object, or, equivalently, *assigned to one bucket* out of all 2^d possible buckets.

^aas far as the assignment of an object to a *bucket* is concerned, the value on which to “split” the attribute’s value’s range can be chosen arbitrarily; two possibly interesting values are discussed in [section 3.2](#).

Like the objects of a sample skyline are assigned to these buckets, the objects of the entire skyline and the entire database are assigned to them, too. This reduces all objects to a scalar in $[0, 2^d] \subset \mathbb{N}$. Each bucket therefore “contains” a number of objects, the objects that have been assigned to each bucket by reducing all their attributes to either “0” or “1”.

Since there are 2^d buckets, it is hard to display a histogram of their distribution. Hence,

W.-T. Balke *et al.* introduce in [6] the idea of *aggregated buckets*, as defined in [definition 3.3](#). Note that the number of buckets combined in order to calculate the aggregated buckets' objects differ for each aggregated bucket, i.e., each aggregated bucket combines $\binom{d}{i}$ buckets, where i is the number of the aggregated bucket, d the dimensionality of each database object. This tends to having more objects assigned to the “center” aggregated buckets than to those at the tails. However, a comparison of the distributions between different subsets of the entire skyline is still plausible since the same method was used, but it is no longer possible to infer which objects in which bucket led to an assignment to an aggregated bucket, e.g., with $d = 3$, an object in the aggregated bucket #2 could originate from one of the buckets 011, 101, or 110.

Definition 3.3 (Aggregated Buckets for Cluster Analysis):

Let B be the set of buckets as defined in [definition 3.2](#) (“Buckets for Cluster Analysis”), with $|B| = 2^d$, d the dimensionality of each database object.

To *aggregate* these buckets, all buckets with the same number of “upper” attributes are consolidated resulting in n *aggregated buckets*.

W.-T. Balke *et al.* propose in [6] to use a value of 0.5 in order to split each attribute's values, such that an object with respect to one attribute is put into the “lower” bucket when its attribute value is in $[0, 0.5) \subset \mathbb{R}$. Consequently, it's put into the “upper” bucket when its attribute value is in $[0.5, 1] \subset \mathbb{R}$. This works well with synthetically generated, randomly distributed data as will be shown in [chapter 4](#) (“Results”). However, since this work benefits from the access to a real world database as described in [section 1.3](#), it may prove beneficial, or offer different insights, if the distribution of each attribute's values is taken into account. In a personal communication with R. Christen, he therefore came up with the idea to use each attribute's values' median as separator criterion. This should reflect the objects' assignment to the buckets (and, subsequently, to the aggregated buckets) more realistically.

In this work, the value 0.5 for every attribute is only used to compare test runs with randomly produced data. For data originating from the real world database, the attribute's values' median is used.

The procedures of calculating the buckets and the aggregated buckets is shown in [algorithm 3.2](#), with [example 3.3](#) illustrating them.

Algorithm 3.2 AggregatedBuckets

Input: S containing database objects, normalized according to [equation \(3.1\)](#).**Output:** Map A containing the aggregated buckets with the assigned $s \in S$.

```

1: Map  $A \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
2:  $B \leftarrow \text{GETBUCKETS}(S)$ 
3: for all  $(b, D) \in B$  do      /*  $b$  is a bucket containing objects from  $S$ ,  $D$  is the set of objects
    within this bucket,  $D \subseteq S$  */
4:   Aggregated bucket number  $a \leftarrow$  number of 1-bits in  $b$ 
5:   if  $\neg \exists A_a$  then
6:      $A_a \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
7:    $A_a \leftarrow A_a \cup \{D\}$ 
8: return  $A$ 

```

Algorithm 3.3 GetBuckets

Input: S containing database objects, normalized according to [equation \(3.1\)](#).Sequence $p \in [0, 1]^n \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ containing the values on which to separate each attribute values in order to assign an attribute to the “lower” or the “upper” attribute bucket.**Output:** Map B containing the buckets with the assigned $s \in S$.

```

1: Map  $B \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
2: for all  $s \in S$  do
3:   Bucket number  $b \leftarrow 0$ 
4:   for  $i \leftarrow 0, |s| - 1$  do      /* iterate over all attributes */
5:     if  $s_i \geq p_i$  then
6:        $b \leftarrow b + 2^i$ 
7:   if  $\neg \exists B_b$  then
8:      $B_b \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
9:    $B_b \leftarrow B_b \cup \{s\}$ 
10: return  $B$ 

```

Example 3.3

Table 3.7 shows an example set S containing database objects with $d = 3$ preferences specified over them, their attributes' values normalized according to equation (3.1).

Object's ID	preference #1	preference #2	preference #3
1	0.0	0.4	1.0
2	1.0	0.5	1.0
3	0.3	0.2	0.0
4	0.3	0.0	0.8
5	0.2	1.0	0.2
Median	0.3	0.4	0.8

Table 3.7: Example objects for cluster analysis

These objects are assigned to buckets as shown in table 3.8. Both variations discussed in section 3.2, taking the arithmetic mean versus taking the median as separation criterion for each attribute bucket, are shown. The buckets are displayed in binary notation to emphasize the connection between bucket number and each object's position in d -dimensional space.

Object's ID	Bucket (mean)	Bucket (median)
1	001	011
2	111	111
3	000	100
4	001	101
5	010	010

Table 3.8: Example objects for cluster analysis bucket assignment

There are 2^d buckets; in this example, most of them empty. When using the arithmetic mean, bucket 000 contains one object, 001 two, 010 one and 111 one. When using each attribute values' median, buckets 010, 011, 100, 101 and 111 contain one object each. To calculate the aggregated buckets, all buckets with the same number of "1" bits are combined. This is shown in table 3.9.

Aggregated Bucket	# objects Buckets (mean)	# objects Buckets (median)
0 (000)	1	0
1 (001, 010, 100)	3	2
2 (011, 101, 110)	0	2
3 (111)	1	1

Table 3.9: Example objects for cluster analysis aggregated bucket assignment

3.3 Dominated Objects

X. Lin *et al.* introduce in [8] another metric for the representativeness of each skyline object: “. . . we quantify the concept of ‘representative’ by the population.” They use this metric to attack the problem they call “top-k RSP (top-k representative skyline points)”, which is assigned to the weighting approaches in [section 1.2](#).

Regrettably, “top-k RSP is NP-hard in a multidimensional space when the dimensionality is 3 [or more]”[8], which is proven in [8]. Hence, they develop and “efficient, scalable randomised algorithm with a theoretical accuracy guarantee”.

However, this work’s not interested in the algorithm, but only in the idea of measuring certain skyline points with respect to the number of objects they dominate. Moreover, for the sake of simplicity, one more property which is fundamental to [8] is ignored in this work: X. Lin *et al.* in [8] need to calculate the *distinct* number of objects a skyline object dominates, meaning “[t]o overcome the over-counting issue, we apply a duplicate-insensitive counting technique”[8]. This is basically what makes top-k RSP hard, and why this is out of scope for this work. Nonetheless, it might be worth future investigations, refer to [chapter 5](#) (“[Conclusion](#)”).

To calculate the metric for this work, for each object of the skyline sample, the *entire database* is iterated over in order to determine whether an object from the database is dominated by this skyline sample object. Obviously, this is a very naïve implementation, but nevertheless the number of dominated objects is obtained. Besides, the runtime is irrelevant to the skyline sampling algorithm, since this calculation is just used to evaluate the skyline sample’s quality.

Consider [example 3.4](#) as an illustration of this metric.

Example 3.4

Consider [figure 1.1](#). Let $\{s_2, s_3\}$ be the skyline sample, while $\{s_1, \dots, s_4\}$ denotes the entire skyline S over the whole database $D = S \cup \{p_1, \dots, p_7\}$.

s_2 dominates $P_2 = \{p_2, p_3, p_4, p_5, p_6\}$ whereas s_3 dominates $P_3 = \{p_4, p_5, p_6, p_7\}$. The entire skyline S dominates $D \setminus S$. However, note that the latter is not always true, since there may well be skyline objects that do not dominate an object in D at all.

The number of objects in the entire database dominated by the skyline sample is $|P_2 \cup P_3|$.

3.4 Representation Error

For Y. Tao *et al.* in *et al.*, retrieving a representative skyline is looked upon as striving for obtaining “. . . a small number k of skyline points that best describe the possible tradeoffs in the full skyline.”[3]. “[A] good representative skyline should be such that, for every nonrepresentative skyline point, there is a nearby representative”[3].

They capture the concept of *representation error* with [equation \(3.2\)](#). Here, S is the entire skyline and $S_{sub} \subset S$ contains the objects which are chosen as the representative subset of S . In this work, S_{sub} equals to the skyline sample. The representation error equals to the nearest neighbour of each object in S_{sub} which is farthest away from its neighbour.

$$Er(S, S_{sub}) = \max_{o \in S \setminus S_{sub}} \{ \min_{p \in S_{sub}} \|o, p\| \} \quad (3.2)$$

Just like the concept discussed in [section 3.3](#), for more than 2 dimensions, the problem is NP-hard which is proven by Y. Tao *et al.* in [3]. However, this work just uses the idea of *representation error* to evaluate the quality of the skyline sample calculated.

Moreover, in order to obtain and evaluate another metric, this work additionally examines the *sum* of the representation error of every object in the skyline sample which is captured by [equation \(3.3\)](#). This idea is explicitly discarded by Y. Tao *et al.* in [3] to be used as base for their calculation of their top k elements of S . However, this work is not concerned about their algorithm, although it may prove beneficial to invest further research into it, refer to [chapter 5](#) (“[Conclusion](#)”). Instead, it aims for the definition of metrics which might offer insights into the quality - the representativeness - of the skyline sample. For this task, the sum of the representation errors has been calculated, examined and interpreted. Nevertheless, it is certainly true that the sum “tends to give more representatives to a dense cluster, because doing so may reduce the distances of a huge number of points to their nearest representatives, which may outweigh the benefit of trying to reduce such distances of points in a faraway sparse cluster”[3]. But the skyline sample is already calculated and is now to be evaluated, the representative objects have already been chosen, so to the contrary, it might prove beneficial to examine the sum of representation errors.

$$ErSum(S, S_{sub}) = \sum_{o \in S \setminus S_{sub}} \{ \min_{p \in S_{sub}} \|o, p\| \} \quad (3.3)$$

Note that [equation \(3.3\)](#) is similar to [definition 3.1](#) (“[Set Coverage](#)”) with respect to the investigation of two objects from different sets with respect to their Euclidean distance. But firstly, with the sum of the representation errors, two sets of unequal cardinality are compared (i.e., for each element in the skyline sample, each element of the entire skyline less the sample itself is investigated). And secondly, not the percentage of objects covered by a second set is reported, but the sum of their Euclidean distances.

Consider [example 3.5](#) as an illustration of these metrics.

Example 3.5

Consider [figure 1.1](#). Let's assume that from the entire skyline, $S = \{s_1, \dots, s_4\}$, a skyline sample is calculated such that it contains $S_{sub} = \{s_1, s_4\}$ (in fact, this would be the skyline sample received when specifying SAMPLE BY RANDOM_SUBSETS COUNT 2 DIMENSION 1 on [figure 1.1](#), since this would yield the skyline object with the lowest price and the skyline object with the lowest mileage).

Clearly, the nearest object of $s_1 \in S_{sub}$ with respect to the Euclidean distance in $S \setminus S_{sub}$ is s_2 , and the nearest object of $s_4 \in S_{sub}$ is s_3 .

Since $\|s_1, s_2\| > \|s_4, s_3\|$, the *representation error* of S_{sub} over S is, according to [equation \(3.2\)](#), $\|s_1, s_2\|$.

The *sum* of the representation error of S_{sub} over S is, in conformity with [equation \(3.3\)](#), $\|s_1, s_2\| + \|s_4, s_3\|$.

Chapter 4

Results

In this chapter, the results according to the discussion about the skyline sample’s quality in [chapter 3](#) (“Skyline Sample Quality”) are evaluated. First of all, test sets are defined on which all the metrics shown are calculated. Special attention has been turned on the *cardinality* of the database attribute’s values, an aspect surprisingly rarely mentioned in the literature consulted for this work.

The aspect of the ability of the prefSQL framework in [\[4\]](#) to specify “OTHERS INCOMPARABLE” over certain preferences has not been investigated, since only a small selection of test sets could be investigated during the development of this work.

Another fixture of the test sets is the set of preferences over which test sets are constructed, refer to [subsection 4.2.1](#) for details. The possible combinations of preferences is huge, and can lead to completely different results when it comes to executing the skyline sampling algorithm. Nonetheless, the test sets chosen are expected to be representative for certain generalizations as will be discussed in the following sections.

4.1 Environment

4.1.1 Hardware

Tests with respect to the evaluation of the runtime have been performed on a dedicated notebook with the following relevant specification:

1. Machine: HP EliteBook 8570w
2. CPU: Intel Core i7-3720QM @ 2.6GHz (4 cores with hyperthreading)
3. OS: Windows 7 Professional SP 1 64 Bit

All other tests not affected by the runtime of the algorithm have been conducted on virtual machines with the following specification:

1. Machine: Virtual machine hosted on a VMware ESXi, 5.5.0 on a SUN FIRE X2270
2. CPU: Intel Xeon E5540 @ 2.53GHz (4 virtual cores)
3. OS: Windows 8.1 Enterprise 64 Bit

Since the implemented algorithm doesn't use parallelised features, the number of cores is irrelevant. The same goes for the harddisk, since I/O operations were not investigated in this work.

4.1.2 Comparison with Random Data

Random data has been generated as sketched in [listing 4.1](#). This is used mainly to perform certain tests which should verify the validity of this work's implementation of the skyline sampling algorithm by comparing the obtained measurements with W.-T. Balke *et al.* in [6].

```

1  DECLARE @RowCount INT
2  DECLARE @Random INT
3  DECLARE @Upper INT
4  DECLARE @Lower INT
5  DECLARE @Range INT
6
7  SET @Lower = 0
8  SET @Upper = 100000
9  SET @RowCount = 1
10 SET @Range = (@Upper - @Lower - 1)
11
12 WHILE @RowCount < 55208
13 BEGIN
14 INSERT INTO [dbo].[CarsRandomData]
15 (...)
16 VALUES
17 (@RowCount, -- primary key
18 (SELECT ROUND((@Range * RAND() + @Lower), 0)), -- numeric column
19 ...
20 (SELECT CAST(ROUND((@Range * RAND() + @Lower), 0) AS VARCHAR(10))), --
    character column
21 ...
22 (SELECT DATEADD(dd, ROUND((@Range * RAND() + @Lower), 0), GETDATE())), -- date
    column
23 ...
24 )
25 SET @RowCount = @RowCount + 1
26 END

```

Listing 4.1: Fill database with Random Data

4.1.3 AutoScout24 Database

In [listing 4.2](#), the structure of the main table “Cars” is depicted. Of the dependent tables used for database normalization, only the “Colors” table is shown for brevity; the others exhibit an analogous structure.

```

1 CREATE TABLE [dbo].[Cars](
2 [Id] [int] NOT NULL,
3 [Make_Id] [int] NOT NULL,
4 [Model_Id] [int] NOT NULL,
5 [Title] [varchar](100) NULL,
6 [Price] [int] NOT NULL,
7 [Mileage] [int] NOT NULL,
8 [Horsepower] [int] NOT NULL,
9 [EngineSize] [int] NOT NULL,
10 [Condition_Id] [int] NOT NULL,
11 [Body_Id] [int] NOT NULL,
12 [Fuel_Id] [int] NOT NULL,
13 [Transmission_Id] [int] NOT NULL,
14 [Drive_Id] [int] NOT NULL,
15 [Color_Id] [int] NOT NULL,
16 [Registration] [date] NOT NULL,
17 [Pollution_Id] [int] NULL,
18 [Efficiency_Id] [int] NULL,
19 [Consumption] [int] NOT NULL,
20 [Doors] [int] NOT NULL,
21 [Seats] [int] NOT NULL,
22 [Cylinders] [int] NOT NULL,
23 [Gears] [int] NOT NULL,
24 [Reference] [varchar](40) NULL,
25 [RegistrationNumeric] [int] NULL,
26 CONSTRAINT [PK_Cars] PRIMARY KEY CLUSTERED
27 (
28 [Id] ASC
29 )WITH (PAD_INDEX = OFF, STATISTICS_NORECOMPUTE = OFF, IGNORE_DUP_KEY = OFF,
        ALLOW_ROW_LOCKS = ON, ALLOW_PAGE_LOCKS = ON) ON [PRIMARY]
30 ) ON [PRIMARY]
31
32 CREATE TABLE [dbo].[Colors](
33 [Id] [int] NOT NULL,
34 [Name] [varchar](20) NULL,
35 [Name_EN] [nvarchar](50) NULL,
36 CONSTRAINT [PK_Colors] PRIMARY KEY CLUSTERED
37 (
38 [Id] ASC
39 )WITH (PAD_INDEX = OFF, STATISTICS_NORECOMPUTE = OFF, IGNORE_DUP_KEY = OFF,
        ALLOW_ROW_LOCKS = ON, ALLOW_PAGE_LOCKS = ON) ON [PRIMARY]
40 ) ON [PRIMARY]

```

Listing 4.2: AutoScout24 Database Structure

4.2 Test Setup

4.2.1 Test Sets

Various test sets have been defined in order to capture different aspects of the skyline sample produced. [Table 4.1](#) shows the base parameters from which the sets have been picked.

Parameter	Possible values
Preference sets	LowCardinality (LCard), HighCardinality (HCard), LowAndHighCardinality (LHCard), All ¹⁴ , ForRandom10 (R10) ¹⁵ , ForRandom17 (R17) ¹⁵
COUNT	10, 15, 30
DIMENSION	3, 5
Test repetitions	20, 100, 1000
Skyline algorithm ¹⁶	SkylineBNL, SkylineBNLSort

Table 4.1: Base parameters from which the test sets have been chosen.

As depicted in [table 4.1](#), certain values for a test repetition have been chosen. The number of combinations possible is far too huge to run the skyline sampling algorithm and to calculate all measurements for all of them. [Examples 4.1](#) and [4.2](#) illustrate this circumstance.

LCard and HCard are expected to uncover the differences in the behaviour of the skyline sampling algorithm with respect to the cardinality of a database’s attributes’ values. In order to obtain a more realistic impression, LHCard and All are defined, which both combine preferences of low and high cardinality. The random sets R10 and R17 are defined to compare the results to those promised by W.-T. Balke *et al.* in [\[6\]](#).

Different COUNT and DIMENSION parameters have been chosen which should provide for discovering differences dependent on these parameter settings.

For combinations of these parameters, test sets are picked as shown in [table 4.2](#). Each of those test sets in turn execute the skyline sampling algorithm for all combinations possible, which is elaborated on below. However, for each of those combinations, the skyline sampling algorithm is executed as many times as the parameter Test repetitions specifies. [Example 4.2](#) illustrates this.

¹⁴defined by M. Galli’s prefSQL framework in [\[4\]](#)

¹⁵for tests with random data only, refer to [subsection 4.1.2](#)

¹⁶as implemented in M. Galli’s prefSQL framework in [\[4\]](#)

Example 4.1

Consider a relatively small set of 9 preferences and a skyline sample of COUNT 10 DIMENSION 3 with 1000 test repetitions; such a setting is covered by the LCard/10/3/1000/BNL test set in [table 4.4](#).

First of all, the number of possible combinations for the subsets of dimension $m = 3$ is $\binom{9}{3} = 84$. Of these 84 subsets, 10 are chosen randomly in order to calculate a subset skyline of COUNT 10 DIMENSION 3. Hence, the number of possible combinations sums up to $\binom{\binom{9}{3}}{10} = \binom{84}{10} \sim 2.7610 \cdot 10^{12}$. This number grows significantly for larger sets of preferences and combinations, e.g. for test set LHCARD/30/5/20/BNL, the number becomes $\binom{\binom{17}{5}}{30} = \binom{6188}{30} \sim 1.9601 \cdot 10^{81}$. There are test sets where these numbers are much smaller. Nevertheless, for all but combinations over very small sets of preferences, it remains computationally infeasible to calculate all combinations.

The time to calculate the skyline sample for the test set LCard/10/3/1000/BNL for just one out of the $\binom{10}{9} = 10$ combinations was on average about 25 minutes, not accounting for the significant cost of the calculations necessary in order to elicit the various metrics, see [subsection 4.2.1](#). It is computationally infeasible with the hardware used in this work to calculate a number of samples 9 orders of magnitude larger.

However, to be precise, the numbers provided in this example are a bit smaller because of the constraints specified in [equation \(2.1\)](#). Nonetheless, in general, this proves to be insignificant: In order to remove the combinations prohibited by [equation \(2.1\)](#) by applying the inclusion-exclusion principle and therefore calculating $\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} -1^i \cdot \binom{n}{i} \cdot \binom{\binom{n-i}{m}}{q}$, the above numbers are hardly affected at all: $\sim 2.4472 \cdot 10^{12}$ instead of $\sim 2.7610 \cdot 10^{12}$ combinations, resp. $\sim 1.9591 \cdot 10^{81}$ instead of $\sim 1.9601 \cdot 10^{81}$ combinations. There are test sets where the difference between these two numbers is bigger, nevertheless, it remains computationally infeasible to calculate all combinations. This aspect has been discussed with user “Brian M. Scott” at math.stackexchange.com.^a

^aaccessible at <http://math.stackexchange.com/questions/1322893/how-many-combinations-s-t-choose-m-of-combinations-t-n-choose-k-ex/1322970#1322970>

Example 4.2

Consider the test set “LCard/30/5/100/BNL” as an example. The results for this test set are based on:

- “LCard/...”: The preference set, which is LCard, as specified in [table 4.2](#). According to [table 4.2](#), LCard specifies 10 preferences. Of these, all possible combinations of $\binom{10}{9=10}$ are built, as specified in column “Comb.”. This means that there will actually be 10 test sets, each test set omitting exactly one preference. This has nothing to do with the subsets of the skyline sampling algorithm, it just serves as a means to easier specify a larger number of test sets while in turn possibly exploiting differences between them based on the small change within the set of preferences.
- “.../30/5/...”: For all of these 10 test sets, the parameters for the skyline sampling algorithm become COUNT 30 DIMENSION 5.
- “.../100/...”: For each of these 10 test sets, the skyline sampling algorithm is executed with the given, unaltered parameters for COUNT and DIMENSION 100 times. With an astronomically high probability (refer to [example 4.1](#)), each of these test repetitions will be based on a different set of subsets of preferences over which each subset skyline is calculated. In this example, for “LCard/30/5/100/BNL”, there are $\sum_{i=0}^{10-1} -1^i \cdot \binom{10}{i} \cdot \binom{10-i}{5} \sim 9.0181 \cdot 10^{28}$. Of these, a mere 100 is chosen.
- “.../BNL/”: For every calculation of a subset skyline, the BNL algorithm is chosen.

[Table 4.2](#) describes the preferences listed in [table 4.1](#) in more detail. For an example more detail, refer to [example 4.2](#).

[Table 4.3](#) shows the cardinality of the database’s columns when the preferences are specified as shown in [table 4.2](#). Note that for the category preferences (e.g., “transmissions.name (‘manual’ >> ‘automatic’ >> OTHERS EQUAL)”), the cardinality of the column depends on the formulation of the preference. With the “OTHERS EQUAL”-clause, the remaining values not specified in the preference are unified and treated as a single value (e.g., the value 0 is assigned to the value ‘manual’, the value 100 to ‘automatic’, and the value 200 to all other values. For more detail, refer to [\[4\]](#)).

From the base parameters shown in [table 4.1](#), the combinations shown in [table 4.4](#) have been chosen in order to obtain the measurements.

Preference set	Comb.	SKYLINE OF ...
LCard	$\binom{10}{9}$	transmissions.name ('manual' >> 'automatic' >> OTHERS EQUAL), drives.name ('front wheel' >> 'all wheel' >> 'rear wheel' >> OTHERS EQUAL), conditions.name ('new' >> 'occasion' >> 'demonstration car' >> 'oldtimer' >> OTHERS EQUAL), doors HIGH, fuels.name ('petrol' >> 'diesel' >> 'bioethanol' >> 'electro' >> 'gas' >> 'hybrid' >> OTHERS EQUAL), gears HIGH, cylinders HIGH, seats HIGH, Body_Id HIGH, Color_Id HIGH
HCard	$\binom{8}{7}$	mileage LOW, price LOW, Model_Id HIGH, engine-size HIGH, horsepower HIGH, registrationNumeric HIGH, consumption LOW, Make_Id HIGH
LHCard	$\binom{18}{17}$	LCard \cup HCard
All	$\binom{17}{16}$	price LOW, mileage LOW, horsepower LOW, enginesize LOW, consumption LOW, doors HIGH, seats HIGH, cylinders HIGH, gears HIGH, registrationNumeric HIGH, colors.name ('red' >> 'blue' >> 'green' >> 'gold' >> 'black' >> 'gray' >> 'bordeaux' >> OTHERS EQUAL), bodies.name ('bus' >> 'cabriolet' >> 'limousine' >> 'coupé' >> 'van' >> 'estate car' >> OTHERS EQUAL), fuels.name ('petrol' >> 'diesel' >> 'bioethanol' >> 'electro' >> 'gas' >> 'hybrid' >> OTHERS EQUAL), makes.name ('BENTLEY' >> 'DAIMLER' >> 'FIAT' >> 'FORD' >> OTHERS EQUAL), conditions.name ('new' >> 'occasion' >> 'demonstration car' >> 'oldtimer' >> OTHERS EQUAL), drives.name ('front wheel' >> 'all wheel' >> 'rear wheel' >> OTHERS EQUAL), transmissions.name ('manual' >> 'automatic' >> OTHERS EQUAL)
R10 ^a	$\binom{10}{7}$	price LOW, mileage LOW, horsepower LOW, enginesize LOW, consumption LOW, doors HIGH, seats HIGH, cylinders HIGH, gears HIGH, registrationNumeric HIGH
R17 ^a	$\binom{17}{16}$	R10 \cup Body_Id HIGH, Color_Id LOW, Make_Id LOW, Model_Id HIGH, Drive_Id HIGH, Transmission_Id HIGH, Fuel_Id LOW

Table 4.2: Preferences specified in the test set preference sets.

^anote that the preferences specified here are semantically completely meaningless, since R10 as well as R17 are used together with randomized data. They just provide for the means to be used directly for the implemented skyline sampling algorithm, and just specify whether a column is preferred to have LOW or HIGH values. Note the different cardinalities listed in table 4.3, too.

Preference	Preference set(s)	DB ^a	Cardinality
transmissions.name ('manual' >> 'automatic' >> OTHERS EQUAL)	LCard, LHCard, All	A	2
drives.name ('front wheel' >> 'all wheel' >> 'rear wheel' >> OTHERS EQUAL)	LCard, LHCard, All	A	3
conditions.name ('new' >> 'occasion' >> 'demonstration car' >> 'oldtimer' >> OTHERS EQUAL)	LCard, LHCard, All	A	4
doors HIGH	LCard, LHCard, All	A	4
makes.name ('BENTLEY' >> 'DAIMLER' >> 'FIAT' >> 'FORD' >> OTHERS EQUAL)	All	A	5
fuels.name ('petrol' >> 'diesel' >> 'bioethanol' >> 'electro' >> 'gas' >> 'hybrid' >> OTHERS EQUAL)	LCard, LHCard, All	A	6
gears HIGH	LCard, LHCard, All	A	7
bodies.name ('bus' >> 'cabriolet' >> 'limousine' >> 'coupé' >> 'van' >> 'estate car' >> OTHERS EQUAL)	All	A	7
cylinders HIGH	LCard, LHCard, All	A	8
colors.name ('red' >> 'blue' >> 'green' >> 'gold' >> 'black' >> 'gray' >> 'bordeaux' >> OTHERS EQUAL)	All	A	8
seats HIGH	LCard, LHCard, All	A	10
Body_Id HIGH	LCard, LHCard	A	11
Color_Id HIGH	LCard, LHCard	A	17
Make_Id HIGH	HCard, LHCard	A	71
consumption LOW	HCard, LHCard, All	A	181
registrationNumeric HIGH	HCard, LHCard, All	A	270
horsepower HIGH	HCard, LHCard, All	A	397
enginesize HIGH	HCard, LHCard, All	A	507
Model_Id HIGH	HCard, LHCard	A	813
price LOW	HCard, LHCard, All	A	5988
mileage LOW	HCard, LHCard, All	A	6515
all preferences over the randomized database	R10, R17	R	[42202,42524]

Table 4.3: Cardinalities of the columns with respect to the specified preferences.

^aA = AutoScout24 as described in section 1.3, R = Random database as described in subsection 4.1.2

Test set	Preferences	CNT	DIM	Repetitions	Algorithm
LCard/10/3/20/BNL	LCard	10	3	20	BNL
LCard/10/3/100/BNL	LCard	10	3	100	BNL
LCard/10/3/1000/BNL	LCard	10	3	1000	BNL
LCard/10/5/20/BNL	LCard	10	5	20	BNL
LCard/10/5/100/BNL	LCard	10	5	100	BNL
LCard/30/3/100/BNL	LCard	30	3	100	BNL
LCard/30/5/100/BNL	LCard	30	5	100	BNL
LCard/10/5/20/Sort	LCard	10	5	20	BNLSort
HCard/10/3/20/BNL	HCard	10	3	20	BNL
HCard/10/3/1000/BNL	HCard	10	3	1000	BNL
HCard/10/5/20/BNL	HCard	10	5	20	BNL
HCard/10/5/20/Sort	HCard	10	5	20	BNLSort
HCard/30/3/20/BNL	HCard	30	3	20	BNL
LHCard/15/3/20/BNL	LHCard	15	3	20	BNL
LHCard/15/5/20/BNL	LHCard	15	5	20	BNL
LHCard/30/3/20/BNL	LHCard	30	3	20	BNL
LHCard/30/5/20/BNL	LHCard	30	5	20	BNL
LHCard/30/5/20/Sort	LHCard	30	5	20	BNLSort
All/15/3/20/BNL	All	15	3	20	BNL
All/15/5/20/BNL	All	15	5	20	BNL
All/30/3/20/BNL	All	30	3	20	BNL
All/30/5/20/BNL	All	30	5	20	BNL
All/30/5/20/Sort	All	30	5	20	BNLSort
R10/10/3/20/BNL	R10	10	3	20	BNL
R10/10/5/20/BNL	R10	10	5	20	BNL
R17/10/3/20/BNL	R17	10	3	20	BNL
R17/10/5/20/BNL	R17	10	5	20	BNL

Table 4.4: Combinations of the base parameters for the test sets.

4.2.2 Measurements

For all the test sets listed in [subsection 4.2.1](#), the following measurements are taken:

- The time it took for skyline sampling algorithm to be executed. Refer to [section 4.1](#) for the hardware the runtime was measured on.
- The size of the skyline sample.

Aside from the time and the skyline sample size which are only taken for the skyline sample algorithm and the skyline sample itself, all measurements are taken for:

- The skyline sample S .
- A random subset R of the entire skyline E , $|R| = |S|$.
- The TOP $|S|$ elements of the entire skyline ordered by BEST_RANK(), which sorts the elements of E by their highest ranking of each attribute, refer to [4].¹⁷
- The TOP $|S|$ elements of the entire skyline ordered by SUM_RANK(), which sorts the elements of E by the highest sum of their rankings of each attribute, refer to [4].¹⁷

For all measurements listed above, the following metrics are calculated once over all the test repetitions of each combination of preferences in each preference set (refer to subsection 4.2.1), and once over all of these combinations:

- The minimum value of the test results S : $\min_{a \in S} a$.
- The maximum value of the test results S : $\max_{a \in S} a$.
- The average, i.e., arithmetic mean, $\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n a_i$.
- The median $\tilde{x} = a_{\frac{n+1}{2}}$ resp. $\tilde{x} = \frac{a_{\frac{n}{2}} + a_{\frac{n}{2}+1}}{2}$.
- The first and third quartile as the median of $[a_1, a_{\tilde{x}}]$ resp. $[a_{\tilde{x}}, a_n]$.
- The unbiased sample variance $s^2 = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (a_i - a_{\bar{x}})^2$.
- The variation coefficient $\hat{c}_v = \frac{\sqrt{s^2}}{\bar{x}}$.

In this work, confidence intervals for the measurements obtained were not calculated, although briefly considered. However, consider that only a tiny fraction of the possible combinations can be tested (example 4.1). Moreover, it would require additional research in order to propose a hypothesis about the distribution of the population of the database objects with respect to individual user preferences. To just assume a normal distribution by assuming that the law of large numbers will apply seems too bold, especially for the real world database used which certainly doesn't contain such a large number of objects (see subsection 4.1.3). However, since the distribution of the population is not known, calculating an upper and lower confidence interval by applying a resampling method like bootstrapping might have proven to be beneficial nonetheless, but this was deemed as out of scope for this work by the author.

4.2.3 Aspects and This Work's Proposed Hypotheses

For all the following aspects, the variation coefficient is expected to decrease with an increasing number of test repetitions. However, since only a tiny fraction of the possible combinations can be tested (refer to example 4.1), it may well be that this aspect falls short of those expectations.

Throughout the following figures, note that whenever the variation coefficient is displayed,

¹⁷In a personal communication with M. Pouly during the discussion of the metrics used by W.-T. Balke *et al.* in [6] to assess the quality of the skyline sample calculated, he came up with the idea to compare the skyline sample with the already existing approaches in the prefSQL framework in [4] of choosing a number of objects from the entire skyline ordered by BEST_RANK() or SUM_RANK(), resp. this led to deeper insights into these two approaches as shown in this chapter.

it’s scale is on the secondary y-axis to the right.

Most of the figures display the average over all test repetitions and test runs. Hence, outliers may remain undetected in the following figures.

Practicable Runtime

W.-T. Balke *et al.* claim in [6] that the skyline sampling algorithm “is generally two to three orders of magnitude faster than computing the entire skyline”. However, they’re using “a database containing 100,000 objects in different synthesized score distributions”, which will likely show different characteristics than the real world database of AutoScout24 (refer to [subsection 4.1.3](#)). Nonetheless:

1. A significant gain in calculation time should be observable when calculating a skyline sample over real world data.
2. It is expected that the runtime is shorter the smaller a test set’s COUNT and DIMENSION parameters are, since the smaller these parameters, the less calculations have to be performed.
3. The BNL algorithm should show better performance than the BNLSort algorithm with small COUNT values, and a break-even should be reached at some point as COUNT grows.
4. The skyline sampling algorithm is expected to be dominated with respect to the runtime by the BNL skyline algorithm that calculates the subset skylines. In other words, the calculations performed by the skyline sampling algorithm alone should not be of great significance for the total runtime. This is expected to be different for the BNLSort algorithm, since for this algorithm, the database has to be sorted before calculating each subset skyline, which is expected to have a more noticeable, negative impact on the runtime.
5. Test sets based on the LCard preference set are expected to show shorter runtime than test sets based on HCard, since for database columns with higher cardinality, a larger number of comparisons between objects should be assumed.
6. The runtime for the R10 and R17 test sets should show similar gains in runtime as experienced in [6] and thereby show the quality of this work’s implementation of the skyline sampling algorithm.

Manageable Skyline Sample Size

W.-T. Balke *et al.* claim in [6] that the skyline sampling algorithm exposes “a difference of two orders of magnitude between out sample and the actual skyline”. However, as already discussed above they’re using synthesized data. Nonetheless:

1. The size of a skyline sample calculated over real world data is expected to be significantly smaller than the size of the entire skyline.
2. It is expected that the size is smaller the smaller a test set’s COUNT and DIMENSION parameters are. The smaller the DIMENSION is, the narrower the topic of interest inves-

tigated is. As shown in [example 2.1](#), a skyline sample over a single preference may well report just a single database object (albeit calculating a subset skyline over just one dimension is discouraged, for that reason). A small value for COUNT might rise the probability to exclude topics of interest which yield many objects, although the effect on the skyline sample size isn't expected to be as prominent as a low value for DIMENSION.

3. Test sets based on the LCard preference set are expected to show smaller skyline samples than test sets based on HCard, since data is expected to be less sparse in higher dimensions when the cardinality of each attribute is small. With higher cardinalities, the curse of dimensionality is expected to become more prominent.
4. The R10 and R17 test sets should show similar gains in skyline size as experienced in [\[6\]](#) and thereby show the quality of this work's implementation of the skyline sampling algorithm.

Set Coverage

W.-T. Balke *et al.* claim in [\[6\]](#) that “with very little variance”, the expectable set coverage for two randomly chosen subsets of the same cardinality “is around 60%”. The set coverage for a skyline sample is expected to show “values around 54% with small variance”. Again, as already discussed above they're using synthesized data. Hence, applied to real world data, the method of set coverage may well yield different measurements. The following is expected:

1. The set coverage between two random samples is expected to be around the values determined in [\[6\]](#). Indeed, the distribution of the real world data differs from synthesized data and certain clusters are expected, which should yield different distributions in the random subsets, too. But those distributions should in turn show up with a similar probability for each random subset chosen, such that the distribution of database objects is expected to be cancelled out.
2. The set coverage of a skyline sample over a randomly chosen subset of the same cardinality, however, is expected to be lower than the experienced 54% in [\[6\]](#). The skyline sample is expected to be influenced by the distribution of objects in the database and should therefore yield a more biased subset than the randomly chosen subset, which is expected to manifest in a lower set coverage.
3. The R10 and R17 test sets should expose similar set coverage as discovered in [\[6\]](#).

Cluster Analysis

W.-T. Balke *et al.* claim in [\[6\]](#) that the “sample's distribution aligns smoothly with the original skyline”, and shows a “distinct shift to the higher buckets”, which they interpret as indicators that the skyline sample's distribution is representative for the entire skyline's distribution. Once again, differences are to be expected between synthesized and real world data. Differences between the resulting histograms are only estimated by looking at them (which is what [\[6\]](#) did, too). Should the desire arise in future requirements to obtain more reliable statements, the calculation of additional metrics like the Bhattacharyya distance between histograms is advised. In this work, this was deemed out of scope by the author. The following is expected:

1. Using the median of each attribute as separator value should come close to the observations in [6], since this respects the structure of the database objects more realistically.
2. The R10 and R17 test sets should expose similar values for the cluster analysis as discovered in [6], both for using 0.5 as well as the median (which should be very similar anyway) as separator for the attribute buckets.
3. The R10 and R17 test sets should provide for similar observations as shown in [6].

Dominated Objects

1. The larger the skyline, the more objects are expected to be dominated. This is not necessarily true for all possible distributions of database objects, but since the entire skyline dominates the rest of the database (aside from objects in the skyline not dominating any other object) and certain dimensions are disregarded by subset skylines, it seems plausible to expect such an observation.

Representation Error

1. The representation error is expected to be smaller the bigger the skyline sample size is.
2. The sum of the representation error is expected to be smaller the bigger the skyline sample size is.

4.3 Practicable Runtime

The skyline sampling algorithm is expected to be dominated by the runtime of the BNL algorithm executed for each subset skyline. If the BNLSort algorithm is used, much runtime is expected to be lost because of re-sorting the database before each subset skyline calculation. The measurements taken from Visual Studio's profiler as depicted in [table 4.5](#) seem to support this expectation.

Step of skyline sampling algorithm	LCard/10/3/20/BNL	HCard/10/3/20/BNL	LHCard/15/3/20/BNL	LCard/10/3/20/BNLSort	HCard/10/3/20/BNLSort	LHCard/15/3/20/BNLSort
Prepare data for skyline algorithm ^a	0.0	0.0	0.0	31.72	84.70	69.12
Execute the skyline algorithm ^b	98.62	95.57	97.63	66.45	13.82	29.76
Eliminate dominated objects ^c	0.75	2.95	1.32	1.04	1.15	0.64
Remaining tasks	0.63	1.48	1.05	0.79	0.33	0.48

Table 4.5: Percentage of runtime used in order to calculate the skyline sample

^ai.e., sort the database if required by the skyline algorithm, i.e., when the BNLSort algorithm is used; refer to [line 5](#) (“Skyline Sampling”).

^brefer to [line 6](#) (“Skyline Sampling”).

^crefer to [line 8](#) (“Skyline Sampling”).

[Figures 4.1 to 4.6](#) summarize the result of the experiments conducted on the skyline samples’ calculation time. Not all skyline samples, namely the test sets based on the LCard preferences set, have been calculated faster than their corresponding entire skylines, which is unexpected. Note the logarithmic scale on the y-axis showing the time in milliseconds.

The skyline samples over the test sets based on the LCard preferences set showed very poor performance. Further research would be necessary to inspect this behaviour closer. The skyline samples over the test sets based on the HCard preferences set, however, expose expected behaviour, they are calculated about one to two orders of magnitude faster than the entire skyline. The preference sets with mixed cardinality show at least a runtime of about one order of magnitude faster. This is not what is claimed in [\[6\]](#). For higher dimensions and random data, however, the claims in [\[6\]](#) seem to hold, since for the R17 test sets, a performance improvement of about two to three orders of magnitude seems indeed achievable.

The BNLSort skyline algorithm performs in general better than its BNL counterpart. However, this is not true, and expectedly so, when it comes to the skyline sampling algorithm. Since there are many sorting operations to be carried out before each subset skyline can be calculated when using the BNLSort skyline algorithm, the performance is worse compared to the BNL algorithm. At least, one benefit shows up upon examining the variation coefficient; when using the BNLSort skyline algorithm, assumptions about the runtime are much more robust than when using the BNL skyline algorithm.

Figure 4.1: Averages Time LCard/*

Figure 4.2: Averages Time HCard/*

Figure 4.3: Averages Time LHCARD/*

Figure 4.4: Averages Time All/*

Figure 4.5: Averages Time R10/*

Figure 4.6: Averages Time R17/*

4.4 Manageable Skyline Sample Size

Figures 4.7 to 4.12 summarize the result of the experiments conducted on the skyline samples' sizes. All skyline samples are smaller than the corresponding entire skyline, which was expected. Note the logarithmic scale.

The skyline samples over the test sets based on the LCard preferences set are about an order of magnitude smaller than those samples based on other preference sets. However, the entire skyline over LCard is very small in the first place, such that the skyline sample size is about half the size of the entire skyline at best. This offers not much benefit and is certainly not what is claimed by W.-T. Balke *et al.* in [6] for their synthesized data. Note that the variation coefficient and the distribution is very stable across multiple runs with the same parameters COUNT and DIMENSION in each test set. Hence, it might be justified to assert that the size of the skyline sample reported is within a rather predictable range when some test runs over a database were performed and the size of the reported skyline sample was measured.

The other test sets show more promising results with respect to a smaller size of the skyline sample. With test sets based on the HCard preferences set and DIMENSION 3, the size is about an order of magnitude smaller than the entire skyline. This is not what is claimed in [6] for their synthesized data, but a significant improvement nonetheless. The outliers make it hard to predict a skyline sample size with a reasonable degree of certainty, but most of the times, the range of the sizes is not too large. With higher DIMENSION, the improvement in more manageable size quickly dissolves, as shown in the HCard/10/5/20/BNL test set.

When preferences over attributes with low as well as high cardinality are specified, which might be reasonably assumed for real world applications and as it is the case for test sets based on the LHCARD and All preferences sets, observations tell that the sizes are about 10 to 20 times smaller than the entire skyline. Although around 1,000 objects (1.8% of the entire database) still pose a challenge when faced with the task to present them to the user, this should in general be easier than presenting her 20,000 objects (36.2% of the entire database). This is not too far off from the claims in [6].

When it comes to random data, this is the fairest comparison with what is claimed in [6]. For a small set of preferences like R10, the skyline sample size is about an order of magnitude smaller than the entire skyline for DIMENSION 3. When DIMENSION increases, the benefit in size becomes insignificant. However, for the R17 preferences set, the skyline sample size for DIMENSION 3 is indeed two orders of magnitudes smaller than the entire skyline, for DIMENSION 5 one order of magnitude. This is well within the range promised in [6], which seems to emphasize the quality of this work's implementation of the skyline sampling algorithm. Note that the variation coefficient for the R10 and R17 preference sets are extremely small. Hence, for a database of randomly distributed objects, the size of a skyline sample seems highly predictable.

Figure 4.7: Averages Size LCard*/BNL

Figure 4.8: Averages Size HCard*/BNL

Figure 4.9: Averages Size LHCard*/BNL

Figure 4.10: Averages Size All*/BNL

Figure 4.11: Averages Size R10*/BNL

Figure 4.12: Averages Size R17*/BNL

4.5 Set Coverage

Figures 4.13 to 4.18 summarize the result of the experiments conducted on the set coverage.

Test sets based on LCard expose a broader range of the set coverage values's distribution, however, throughout the test sets, the variation coefficient remains relatively low. It is quite clear that for LCard type preferences, for the skyline sample, the representativeness increases with increasing DIMENSION, and even more so with increasing COUNT parameter.

The BEST_RANK as well as the SUM_RANK sets seem to benefit from an increased size. Note that the only difference when it comes to evaluating BEST_RANK and SUM_RANK is the size of the set, which is determined by the size of the skyline sample. Since the sample is bigger for LCard with a higher COUNT parameter, this manifests in a change for BEST_RANK and SUM_RANK, and this change (the bigger size of the set) leads to a higher set coverage.

For HCard type preferences, the set coverage increases dramatically when increasing the DIMENSION parameter. The situation for BEST_RANK and SUM_RANK is analogous to LCard.

For preferences with mixed cardinality, an increased DIMENSION seems beneficial to the set coverage.

All in all, the results reproduce quite well the claims in [6], at least when choosing appropriate parameters COUNT and DIMENSION. With preferences of mixed cardinality, though, it seems harder to reach a higher set coverage.

Another interesting aspect is that the set coverage is seemingly rather invariant when the test repetitions are increased and the other parameters are untouched. This seems to provide for a relatively high degree of certainty that the numbers measured for the set coverage are predictable.

Figure 4.13: Averages Set Coverage LCard*/BNL

Figure 4.14: Averages Set Coverage HCard*/BNL

Figure 4.15: Averages Set Coverage LHCard*/BNL

Figure 4.16: Averages Set Coverage All*/BNL

Figure 4.17: Averages Set Coverage R10*/BNL

Figure 4.18: Averages Set Coverage R17*/BNL

4.6 Cluster Analysis

Figures 4.19 to 4.23 summarize the result of the experiments conducted on the cluster analysis for LCard type preferences.

Figures 4.24 to 4.28 summarize the result of the experiments conducted on the cluster analysis for HCard type preferences.

Figures 4.29 to 4.33 summarize the result of the experiments conducted on the cluster analysis for LHCard type preferences.

Figures 4.34 to 4.38 summarize the result of the experiments conducted on the cluster analysis for All type preferences.

Figures 4.39 to 4.43 summarize the result of the experiments conducted on the cluster analysis for R10 type preferences.

Figures 4.44 to 4.48 summarize the result of the experiments conducted on the cluster analysis for R17 type preferences.

All the results on real world data for the cluster analysis show that the assignment of the objects to their aggregated buckets on average aligns quite closely to the entire skyline. For LCard and HCard type preferences, the histograms are almost identical to the entire skyline. For the LHCard and the All types, there is a bit of a shift away from the entire skyline, but the distributions are still fairly closeby.

Choosing the median as separator value for the buckets has proven to be beneficial, since the characteristics of the database and the skylines are more prominently displayed.

For the sake of brevity, the charts for the BEST_RANK and SUM_RANK approach have been omitted, since they are almost identical to the skyline sample and the random set of same cardinality shown in the charts in the middle of each following page.

The test sets executed on random data, the R10 and R17 types, show an extremely low variation coefficient. The variation is much more prominent when analysing real world data, which means that more test runs would be necessary to achieve the same certainty about the distributions as it can be observed when examining the R10 and R17 data. The claims in [6] seem to predict this data quite well, even though they claim a shift to the right compared to the entire database, which cannot be observed here (and wasn't observed in fact by W.-T. Balke *et al.* in [7], so this seems to be of rather low significance). However, the shift of the entire skyline compared to the skyline sample in the R17 sets seems to show some significance; more test runs would be necessary to confirm or contradict this observation.

Figure 4.19: Cluster Analysis LCard Entire DB

Figure 4.20: Cluster Analysis LCard Entire Skyline

Figure 4.21: Cluster Analysis LCard Skyline Sample

Figure 4.22: Cluster Analysis LCard Random

Figure 4.23: Cluster Analysis LCard Averages

Figure 4.24: Cluster Analysis HCard Entire DB

Figure 4.25: Cluster Analysis HCard Entire Skyline

Figure 4.26: Cluster Analysis HCard Skyline Sample

Figure 4.27: Cluster Analysis HCard Random

Figure 4.28: Cluster Analysis HCard Averages

Figure 4.29: Cluster Analysis LHCARD Entire DB

Figure 4.30: Cluster Analysis LHCARD Entire Skyline

Figure 4.31: Cluster Analysis LHCARD Skyline Sample

Figure 4.32: Cluster Analysis LHCARD Random

Figure 4.33: Cluster Analysis LHCARD Averages

Figure 4.34: Cluster Analysis All Entire DB

Figure 4.35: Cluster Analysis All Entire Skyline

Figure 4.36: Cluster Analysis All Skyline Sample

Figure 4.37: Cluster Analysis All Random

Figure 4.38: Cluster Analysis All Averages

Figure 4.39: Cluster Analysis R10 Entire DB

Figure 4.40: Cluster Analysis R10 Entire Skyline

Figure 4.41: Cluster Analysis R10 Skyline Sample

Figure 4.42: Cluster Analysis R10 Random

Figure 4.43: Cluster Analysis R10 Averages

Figure 4.44: Cluster Analysis R17 Entire DB

Figure 4.45: Cluster Analysis R17 Entire Skyline

Figure 4.46: Cluster Analysis R17 Skyline Sample

Figure 4.47: Cluster Analysis R17 Random

Figure 4.48: Cluster Analysis R17 Averages

4.7 Dominated Objects

Figures 4.49 to 4.54 summarize the result of the experiments conducted on the dominated objects.

Not many conclusions may be drawn from these results, regrettably. In general, the number of dominated objects increases with increasing COUNT and DIMENSION, which was expected. Please note that the scale of the y-axis had to be adjusted for LCard type preferences because of their extremely low variation coefficient.

The variation for the other sets in general is very high, such that it seems bold to draw any more conclusions based on this data. There seem to be patterns connected to a variation in COUNT and DIMENSION parameters, but with this variance, it is hard to draw conclusions. Clearly, many more test runs would be necessary in order to make reliable statements.

The R10 and R17 preferences expose interesting behaviour, nonetheless. They both show a very low variation coefficient, and the number of objects dominated by the skyline sample is significantly less for the R17 preference set, which is, for more dimensions. This may be interpreted as a manifestation of the curse of dimensionality, which states that the more dimensions, the sparser the data becomes, i.e., the less objects are dominated with respect to all dimensions.

Under this impression, leaving aside the huge variation of HCard, LHCard and All preference sets, the curse of dimensionality seems to manifest in these sets, too; at the very least, LCard shows almost all database objects dominated no matter what other parameters have been chosen, and the LHCard and All preference sets tend to have their highest population density around 10,000 - 20,000 objects. With HCard, at least for a low DIMENSION parameter, this seems to uphold, too.

Figure 4.49: Averages Dominated Objects LCard*/BNL

Figure 4.50: Averages Dominated Objects HCard*/BNL

Figure 4.51: Averages Dominated Objects LHCard*/BNL

Figure 4.52: Averages Dominated Objects All*/BNL

Figure 4.53: Averages Dominated Objects R10*/BNL

Figure 4.54: Averages Dominated Objects R17*/BNL

4.8 Representation Error

Representation Error of Worst Element

Figures 4.55 to 4.60 summarize the result of the experiments conducted on the representation error.

The charts show a very prominent trend that the higher the COUNT and DIMENSION parameters are, the lower the representation error gets, which is what was expected. Just like the set coverage, these numbers remain very similar even when increasing the test repetitions, which should provide for the assumption that the values are predictable for future test runs.

For HCard, the representation error is even lower than for LCard or the LHCard and All preference sets.

The SUM_RANK approach shows some deficits here, in all preference sets, its representation errors are significantly higher than for BEST_RANK, the skyline sample or even randomly chosen objects.

The R10 and R17 preference sets show a very low variation, but their averages fluctuate in a similar way as the sets based on real world data.

Figure 4.55: Averages Representation Error LCard*/BNL

Figure 4.56: Averages Representation Error HCard*/BNL

Figure 4.57: Averages Representation Error LHCARD*/BNL

Figure 4.58: Averages Representation Error All*/BNL

Figure 4.59: Averages Representation Error R10*/BNL

Figure 4.60: Averages Representation Error R17*/BNL

Representation Error Sum Over All Elements

Figures 4.61 to 4.66 summarize the result of the experiments conducted on the representation error sums.

Note that the y-axis had to be adjusted for almost each chart.

The sum of representation errors shows very different behaviour between test sets based on different preference sets.

LCard, in general, shows a relatively low error, even more so when increasing the COUNT parameter. Although LCard shows some sensitivity to the DIMENSION parameter, the effect of higher DIMENSION is much more prominent in HCard, the sum of representation errors becoming very low.

For the preference sets LHCard and All, the sum of representation errors is relatively high to begin with, but becomes smaller when increasing COUNT and DIMENSION.

This behaviour seems to provide for the notion that the sum of representation errors declines when calculating more subset skylines and/or subset skylines of larger dimension. Hence, the objects chosen seem to represent the entire skyline the better the bigger these parameters are chosen.

As with the representation error in itself, R10 and R17 show similar behaviour, again with a very low variation.

Figure 4.61: Averages Representation Error Sum LCard*/BNL

Figure 4.62: Averages Representation Error Sum HCard*/BNL

Figure 4.63: Averages Representation Error Sum LHCARD*/BNL

Figure 4.64: Averages Representation Error Sum All*/BNL

Figure 4.65: Averages Representation Error Sum R10*/BNL

Figure 4.66: Averages Representation Error Sum R17*/BNL

Chapter 5

Conclusion

This work has shown the successful implementation and integration of the skyline sampling algorithm as proposed in [6]. The results discussed in [chapter 4](#) have shown valuable insights into a skyline sample under different conditions, which should prove beneficial for future work and research, since without those measurements, it remains hard to imagine whether a sample of a high-dimensional skyline is “representative” or not. It could be shown that the skyline sample itself can be treated as a representative subset of the entire skyline and is not necessarily only of use to provide a first glance on the skyline and only valuable after eliciting more feedback from the user.

When executing the skyline sampling algorithm over new real world databases, its parameters may be adjusted such that the most representative sample is reported. However, as the results suggest, the parameters will have to be chosen with respect to the database values’ structure. Vast differences have been seen when it comes to representativeness aspects with different combinations of cardinalities. In general, with a database containing columns of lower as well as higher cardinality over which preferences are specified, the parameters COUNT and DIMENSION should be chosen as high as possible to improve the representativeness of the sample. On the other hand, this increases the runtime of the skyline sampling algorithm and the size of the reported sample. Hence, a reasonable compromise has to be found, which must respect the individual database content.

The concerns about runtime are of course mainly prominent when using the skyline sampling algorithm online, e.g., on an e-commerce platform. However, when it comes to offline calculation for certain data mining tasks or in order to prepare data a user doesn’t need immediate access to, many more possibilities arise for adjusting the parameters. The skyline algorithm has proven to be robust throughout this work and the final test runs, such that the expectation seems justified that its usage for such tasks will be unproblematic.

Certain behaviours of the skyline sampling algorithm, however, should be investigated by

conducting more research or performing more specific test runs. The tests conducted could only account for a tiny fraction of all the possible combination of how to specify preferences over a database. Especially the runtime behaviour of test sets over preferences with low cardinality should be investigated in detail.

Outlook

There are certain possibilities how ease the pressure on the contradicting aims of practical runtime and manageable sample size on the one hand and achieving a high representativeness on the other.

First of all, the parallel calculation of the subset skylines should improve the runtime when more than one CPU core is available, since those subset skylines can be calculated independently of each other and afterwards merged to report the complete skyline sample. This is expected to provide for faster runtime, thereby opening the possibilities for bigger COUNT and DIMENSION parameters.

The manageability of the sample size might be better controllable by top-k algorithms such as those mentioned within this report, namely [3, 8]. Even though the exact calculation for both approaches are NP-hard, the heuristics they developed might open the possibilities for a more manageable size even without sacrificing the representativeness of the reported subset of the entire skyline.

All in all, the skyline sampling approach shows promising results and the integration into real world applications should be possible quite easily since it could be integrated into M. Galli's prefSQL framework in [4].

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